

HyDelta 4

WP5b – Innovative and sustainable recompression concepts for mobile operation

D5b.1 – Functional specification

Status: Final version

Document summary

Corresponding author

Corresponding author	Leonard van Lier
Affiliation	TNO
Email address	Leonard.vanlier@tno.nl

Document history

Version	Date	Author	Affiliation	Summary of main changes
1	4-Feb-2026	Leonard van Lier, Harry Korst, Robert Mellema	TNO, DNV	First draft
2	13-Mar-2026	Leonard van Lier, Harry Korst, Robert Mellema	TNO, DNV	Second draft, circulated to HyDelta SG
Final	28-Apr-2026	Leonard van Lier, Harry Korst, Robert Mellema	TNO, DNV	Final version, after review by HyDelta SG

Dissemination level

PU	Public	X
RE	Restricted to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project partners including Expert Assessment Group External entity with whom a Non-Disclosure Agreement exists 	

Document review

Partner	Name
Gasunie	Theo Wieleman, Sander Timmers, Ronald Slegers en Arno Oosterhof
NBNL, Gasunie, Kiwa, DNV, TNO, NEC	HyDelta Supervisory Group

Tag (Choose only ONE):

Technology and Safety

- Activities (e.g. maintenance, purging, etc.)
- Assets
- Digitalisation
- End use
- Gas network
- QRA

Social aspects

- Conversion (of the distribution network)
- Education
- Social

System and Economy

- Business Development
- Production and supply
- Value chains

Gas Quality

- Admixing
- Gas Quality
- Odourisation

Executive summary

Compressor design

The compressor type selection shows that the most likely compressor concept to evacuate hydrogen, is a reciprocating i.e. piston compressor. As a design case for this compressor concept, Gasunie has defined quite an ambitious worst-case evacuation scenario, in which an 80km-long, large-diameter pipeline needs to be evacuated in 500 hours from a starting pressure of 67.2 bar(a) to a final pressure in the to-be-evacuated pipe at the end of the evacuation of 1.5 bar(a)¹.

As a first step, a high-level compressor performance analysis has been executed to determine how an ideal hydrogen Re-Compression Unit (RCU) could look like. This analysis shows that at least 4 stages will be required in case the maximum discharge temperature is to remain below 150°C. In case higher cylinder temperatures would be allowed, then a 3-stage compressor might suffice. As a next step in the conceptual designs of the hydrogen RCUs, several market parties have been interviewed to check what could realistically be fitted on a single trailer of standard dimensions (width <2.55m).

The main conclusion of this market scan is that none of the proposed concepts, will be able to fully meet the defined worst-case evacuation scenario. The most promising concept will be a V-type compressor that is equipped with 4 water-cooled lubricated double acting cylinders. Such a compressor will be able to operate with high discharge temperatures and can achieve the high required pressure ratio at the final stages of the evacuation in only 3 (or maximum 4) stages. The only parameter where this compressor concept clearly does not meet the benchmark requirements, will be the evacuation time. In the current RCU market for natural gas, smaller (100kW) units exist which will have less than 10% of the required capacity. As time evolves and the hydrogen recompression market would become more mature, then this compressor concept is likely to be increased in size. Assuming that 300kW or even 500kW units would become available in the future, then 5 or 3 parallel operated units should be able to meet the 500 hours evacuation time. A second important advantage of such a concept is that these units can also easily be deployed for smaller evacuation jobs (which are more likely to occur in a nearer future). Alternative concepts will be of interest for applications in the further future and are discussed in this report as well.

Compressor driver design

In view of the advantages that an electric drive provides, Gasunie has expressed a preference for the use of an indirect drive, i.e. the use of a rented generator set in combination with an electric drive of the compressor. The drive of the semi-truck for transporting the compressor trailer or the generator set can be chosen freely, but it may be appreciated that (bio-)CNG or HVO powered trucks provide advantages in terms of weight over electric vehicles. The rented generator set can be equipped with various drives with their own specific advantages and disadvantages. In this study the following drives and fuels were assessed:

1. Hydrogen powered engine (hydrogen supply from the pipeline to be evacuated);
2. Hydrogen fuelled fuel cell (with external hydrogen supply);
3. Bio-CNG fuelled engine;
4. Natural gas fuelled engine;
5. HVO-fuelled engine;

¹ Or: as low as possible.

6. Bio-methanol fuelled engine;
7. Ammonia fuelled engine.

Based on preferences expressed by Gasunie, it has been determined that the options for driving the generator set based on bio-CNG, HVO and hydrogen are the most favourable when it comes to emission reduction, operational aspects and financial-economic considerations. Which of these three options will be the final preference will have to be determined by Gasunie, but it is also possible to vary between projects.

Samenvatting

Compressor ontwerp

De selectie van het compressortype laat zien dat het meest geschikte compressorconcept voor het evacueren van waterstof een zuigercompressor is. Als ontwerpcase voor dit compressorconcept heeft Gasunie een ambitieus worst-case scenario voor de evacuatie gedefinieerd, waarbij een 80 km lange pijpleiding met een grote diameter in 500 uur moet worden geëvacueerd van een begindruk van 67,2 bar(a) naar een einddruk van 1,5 bar(a)² in de te evacueren pijpleiding.

Als eerste stap is een analyse van de compressor performance op hoofdlijnen uitgevoerd om te bepalen hoe een ideale waterstof-recompressie-eenheid (RCU) eruit zou kunnen zien. Deze analyse toont aan dat er minstens 4 compressie trappen nodig zijn als de maximale uitlaattemperatuur onder de 150 °C moet blijven. Als hogere cilindertemperaturen toegestaan zouden zijn, zou een 3-traps compressor wellicht volstaan. Als volgende stap in het conceptuele ontwerp van de waterstof-RCU's zijn diverse marktpartijen geïnterviewd om te bepalen wat realistisch gezien op een standaard trailer (breedte < 2,55 m) past.

De belangrijkste conclusie van deze marktanalyse is dat geen van de voorgestelde concepten volledig zal voldoen aan het gedefinieerde worst-case scenario voor evacuatie. Het meest veelbelovende concept is een V-type compressor met 4 watergekoelde, gesmeerde, dubbelwerkende cilinders. Zo'n compressor kan werken met hoge uitlaatgastemperaturen en kan de vereiste hoge drukverhouding in de laatste fasen van de evacuatie in slechts 3 (of maximaal 4) stappen bereiken. De enige parameter waar dit compressorconcept duidelijk niet aan de benchmarkvereisten voldoet, is de evacuatietijd. Op de huidige markt voor hercompressie-units (RCU's) voor aardgas zijn kleinere units (100 kW) beschikbaar die minder dan 10% van de vereiste capaciteit hebben. Naarmate de markt voor waterstof her-compressie zich verder ontwikkelt en volwassen wordt, zal dit compressorconcept waarschijnlijk groter worden. Ervan uitgaande dat er in de toekomst units van 300 kW of zelfs 500 kW beschikbaar komen, zouden 5 of 3 parallel geschakelde units de evacuatietijd van 500 uur moeten kunnen halen. Een tweede belangrijk voordeel van een dergelijk concept is dat deze eenheden ook gemakkelijk kunnen worden ingezet voor kleinere evacuatieoperaties (die waarschijnlijk op korte termijn zullen plaatsvinden). Alternatieve concepten zullen interessant zijn voor toepassingen in de verdere toekomst en worden eveneens in dit rapport besproken.

Aandrijving ontwerp

Gezien de voordelen van een elektrische aandrijving heeft Gasunie de voorkeur gegeven aan een indirecte aandrijving, oftewel het gebruik van een gehuurde generator in combinatie met een elektrische aandrijving van de compressor. De aandrijving van de vrachtwagen voor het transport van de compressoroplegger of de generator kan vrij gekozen worden, maar het is belangrijk te weten dat vrachtwagens op (bio-)CNG of HVO een gewichtsvoordeel bieden ten opzichte van elektrische voertuigen. De gehuurde generator kan worden uitgerust met diverse aandrijvingen, elk met hun eigen specifieke voor- en nadelen. In deze studie werden de volgende aandrijvingen en brandstoffen beoordeeld:

1. Motor op waterstof (waterstoftoevoer via de pijpleiding die moet worden afgetapt);
2. Brandstofcel op waterstof (met externe waterstoftoevoer);
3. Motor op bio-CNG;

² Of: zo laag mogelijk

4. Motor op aardgas;
5. Motor op HVO;
6. Motor op biomethanol;
7. Motor op ammoniak.

Op basis van de door Gasunie geuite voorkeuren is vastgesteld dat de aandrijfopties voor de generatorset op basis van bio-CNG, HVO en waterstof het meest gunstig zijn wat betreft emissiereductie, operationele aspecten en financiële overwegingen. Welke van deze drie opties uiteindelijk de voorkeur krijgt, zal door Gasunie moeten worden bepaald, maar dit kan per project verschillen.

Table of contents

Document summary	2
Executive summary	3
Compressor design	3
Compressor driver design	3
Samenvatting.....	5
Compressor ontwerp.....	5
Aandrijving ontwerp.....	5
1. Introduction.....	10
1.1 Recompression of gas	10
1.2 Nomenclature	12
2. Project methodology and benchmark.....	13
2.1 Functional requirements and benchmark description	14
3. Compressor type selection.....	16
3.1 Use case description	16
3.2 Compressor types	16
3.2.1 Reciprocating compressor	18
3.2.2 Screw compressor	20
3.2.3 Centrifugal compressor	22
3.2.4 Non-mechanical compressors	23
3.3 Pro-cons for the recompression use case.....	24
3.4 Hybrid compression options	26
4. Compressor sizing of the most promising concept	27
4.1 Compressor performance evaluation	27
4.1.1 Introduction.....	27
4.1.2 Detailed description worst-case design scenario	27
4.1.3 Required number of compressor stages	28
4.1.4 Maximum allowable discharge temperature	29
4.1.5 Ideal compressor designs	30
4.1.6 Sensitivity analysis	35
4.1.7 Conclusions.....	36
4.2 Practical feedback from compressor packagers/OEM/End Users	36
4.2.1 Introduction.....	36
4.2.2 Compressor concept 1.....	37
4.2.3 Compressor concept 2.....	38

4.2.4	Compressor concept 3	39
4.2.5	Overview of contacted market parties	40
4.2.6	Miscellaneous topics	40
4.3	Conclusions	41
5.	Driver and power supply options	42
5.1	Direct drive option	42
5.2	Indirect drive option	42
5.3	Conceptual design.....	43
5.4	Generator concepts	45
5.4.1	Hydrogen engine	47
5.4.2	Bio-CNG engine.....	48
5.4.3	Natural gas engine	49
5.4.4	HVO engine.....	50
5.4.5	Methanol engine	50
5.4.6	Ammonia engine.....	51
5.4.7	Hydrogen fuel cell.....	52
5.4.8	Batteries.....	54
5.4.9	Battery back-up/peak shaving functionality.....	55
5.4.10	Summary of emissions	56
5.5	Gasunie requirements.....	56
6.	Performance characteristics analysis	57
6.1	Results for the performance aspect ‘Sustainability’	58
6.2	Results for the performance characteristic ‘Technical/operational’	59
6.3	Results for the performance characteristic ‘Business economics’	60
6.3	Conclusions	61
7.	Operational and maintenance aspects.....	62
7.1	Vibrations and noise of natural gas RCU’s	62
7.1.1	Motivation	62
7.1.2	RCU description	62
7.1.3	Test program	64
7.1.4	Vibration measurement results - trailer	66
7.1.5	Vibration measurement results - trailer	67
7.1.6	Vibration measurement results – temporary piping.....	70
7.1.7	Noise measurement results.....	70
7.2	Operation and maintenance	71

References..... 74

1. Introduction

1.1 Recompression of gas

Hydrogen is expected to play a key role in the Dutch energy strategy to decarbonize industries and to provide balance to the renewable energy supply. Besides the national hydrogen transmission infrastructure from HyNetwork Services (HNS), hydrogen distribution grids will need to be developed to connect the HNS backbone with regional supply and demand, and to interconnect supply and demand nodes locally.

Even though the direct impact of hydrogen (on the environment) as a green-house gas is small, the emission to the environment shall be minimized as much as possible. Also for economic reasons, excessive venting or flaring of hydrogen shall be avoided.

Still, the functional requirements of operation of a hydrogen network, like with the existing operation with natural gas, requires periodic evacuation of pipelines. Maintenance or re-purposing of pipelines are the common trigger for such evacuation events. During the evacuation, instead of depressurizing and venting the isolated pipeline segment toward atmosphere, a compressor is used to transfer the gas from the to-be-evacuated pipeline toward a neighbouring line. This neighbouring pipeline can be a separate line, or the same pipeline on the other side of the isolation valves.

Figure 1-1. Example of re-compression within the same pipeline.

Figure 1-2. Example of re-compression to an adjacent pipeline.

For the evacuation of the hydrogen, a compressor is required. The compressor will have to be **efficient** over a **broad range of pressure conditions**. At the start of the evacuation, the inlet pressure may be practically the same as the pressure of the outlet line (pressure ratio ≈ 1). At the end of the evacuation, the pressure in the to-be-evacuated pipeline will have dropped to a low value (as low as possible).

The compressor shall have a sufficient **capacity**, to minimize the evacuation time. The compressor has to be efficient over this large range of pressure conditions, to enable an energy-efficient re-compression process.

The compressor solution has to be a **mobile** unit (placement of permanent compressor packages would be unpractical). This imposes many practical logistic limitations. For example, the transportability shall comply with Dutch and European legislation. Excessive compressor package

sizes will result in unpractical situations, requiring special transportation permits and arrangements. Some remote areas, that are not uncommon for evacuation events, would become also inaccessible for the compressor package. Generally, the mobile compressor solution is mounted on a truck (semi) trailer. Two typical examples are shown below:

Figure 1-3. Example of a mobile, trailer-mounted, compressor package (source: www.lmf.at).

Figure 1-4. Example of a mobile, trailer-mounted, compressor package, operated by Gasunie.

The compressor **driver** has to be a **flexible** and **clean** technical solution. Due to the large range of operating (pressure) conditions during the evacuation, the power demands are also variable, including typical ‘peak moments’ in the consumed power, when the compressor operating mode switches (e.g. from single-stage to multi-stage operation). The driver shall be versatile, so that that can be operated in remote areas, using the cleanest and cheapest available power source (green electricity from network, natural gas engine, hydrogen engine, power generator set with various fuel types). The emissions from the driver shall be considered in the total CO₂ footprint of the evacuation operation.

For natural gas in The Netherlands, a tradition of mobile re-compression products has been developed in the past 2 decades. However, for hydrogen such solutions are not yet available (or only at a very limited scale). In the HyDelta4 research program, a dedicated work package was defined on the development of re-compression concepts for hydrogen. The description of this work is contained in [1]: WP5b “Innovative and sustainable re-compression concepts for mobile operation”.

1.2 Nomenclature

CNG	Compressed Natural Gas
DA	Double acting
Dis.	Discharge
H2 ICE	Hydrogen Internal Combustion Engine
HVO	Hydrotreated Vegetable Oil
JT	Joule Thomson
NCV	Net Calorific Value
P	Pressure in bar(a) - absolute pressure or bar(g) - gauge
QRA	Quantitative Risk Assessment
PPM	Part Per Million
PEM	Proton-Exchange Membrane
PEMFC	Proton-Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell
RCU	Re-Compression Unit
Rev.	Revolution
Suc.	Suction
T	Temperature in °C
UPS	Uninterruptible Power Supply
VFD	Variable Frequency Drive (of the electric motor)
VSD	Variable Speed Drive (of the electric motor)
WP	Work Package

2. Project methodology and benchmark

In the research program of this work package WP5b, TNO was responsible for the overall coordination and execution. Furthermore, TNO handled the compressor selection and sizing for the recompression use case. Another project partner, the research institute DNV, focussed on the selection and sizing of the driver of the compressor, as well as on the operational and maintenance aspects.

To investigate the best options for the use case of mobile hydrogen recompression, first an inventory of available compressor technology was made. The state-of-the-art of compression techniques was investigated and judged for the specific use case of hydrogen recompression. The advantages and disadvantages of the various techniques were weighed in a qualitative way. After this preliminary selection of the most promising concept, the sizing of the compressor was assessed in a more quantitative way. First, based on simplified modelling assumptions for an ideal compressor performance. This sizing was reviewed in detail by a commercial party (compressor packager) that has experience with design of natural gas recompression units. Also the feedback and suggestions from the compressor manufacturer were included in the assessment. Finally the findings and compressor selections were judged by several market parties with experience on the domain of recompression (interviews).

For the selection design and sizing of the driver, an inventory of the options was made by DNV. After feedback by Gasunie (potential end user of the recompression units) a set of weighing factors was compiled that enabled a balanced selection of the best strategy.

During the project several project meetings were held, with TNO, DNV, and the members of the Expert Assessment Group (EAG). The following team was mobilized for the HyDelta4 WP5b project:

Figure 2-1. HyDelta4 WP 5b project team and EAG, with representatives from Gasunie, TNO, DNV and Stedin. Project meeting at Gasunie Special Assignments, Deventer (in front of one of Gasunie's natural gas recompression trailer).

Table 2-1. Project and Expert Assessment Group members, for HyDelta4, WP5b.

Name	Company	Role
Leonard van Lier	TNO	Project coordination and execution
Harry Korst	TNO	Project execution
Robert Mellema	DNV	Project execution
Pieter Wolff	DNV	Project execution
Theo Wieleman	Gasunie	EAG chairman
Arno Oosterhof	Gasunie	EAG member
Sander Timmers	Gasunie	EAG member
Ronald Slegers	Gasunie	EAG member
Gilles de Kok	Stedin	EAG member

2.1 Functional requirements and benchmark description

In the project description, a preliminary benchmark case was defined for the evacuation scenario: “a **80-kilometer** long **48-inch** pipeline should be evacuated from 66.2 bar(g) to (preferably) 0.5 bar(g) in 3 weeks”. This scenario was labelled in the project proposal as a ‘worst-case’, and indeed is considered a formidable volume. For example, a recent construction in The Netherlands of a new hydrogen pipeline between a production facility in Rotterdam and the neighbouring industrial cluster is 30-kilometer long 24-inch. This volume would be ≈ 11 times smaller than the worst-case benchmark in HyDelta4.

During the execution phase of the project, the benchmark was further detailed and specified as follows:

Parameter	Value	Remarks
Evacuation volume	80 km, 48” pipeline ($D_o=1219.0\text{mm}$, wall thickness = 18.3mm)	
Evacuation time	3 weeks (500 hours)	
Start pressure	67.2 bar(a)	This is the maximum operating pressure for HTL network
End pressure	1.5 bar(a)	This is the desired minimum residual pressure in the to-be-evacuated pipeline
Back pressure	67.2 bar(a)	Pressure of the pipeline where the gas is being evacuated to
Inlet temperature	15 °C	
Interstage temperature	15 °C, 40 °C	After-cooler temperature, both values were considered in preliminary sizing

Two hydrogen gas compositions were considered in the preliminary compressor sizing:

Component	Mole percentage	
	Gas composition 1	Gas composition 2
H ₂ – Hydrogen	99.5%	98.0%
N ₂ – Nitrogen	0.25%	1.0%
CH ₄ – Methane	0.25%	1.0%
Mole weight [g/mol]	2.12	2.42

Derived quantities are as follows (using RKS equation-of-state):

Parameter	Value	Remarks
Evacuation pipeline volume	87,873 m ³	Large volume, due to the requirement of spacious valve stations in the transport grid
Start density	5.70 kg/m ³ 6.51 kg/m ³	At 15 °C, composition 1 At 15 °C, composition 2
Total mass, prior to evacuation	501 ton 572 ton	Composition 1 Composition 2
Average polytropic coefficient	1.44	gamma

The focus of the investigation with this benchmark is on the HTL net (high-pressure network), rather than the lower-pressure, smaller line-size RTL network. Still the same technical considerations will be valid for the regional networks.

3. Compressor type selection

3.1 Use case description

The use case that will be used for the compressor type selection is in fact the worst-case benchmark case discussed in section 2.1. The most relevant aspects for the considerations of the different compressor types are:

- Medium: high-purity hydrogen (>98%), molecular weight=2.1-2.4 g/mol
- Variable inlet pressure conditions (1.5-67.2 bar(a))
- Variable outlet pressure conditions (28-67.2 bar(a))
- Large capacity required (>500 kW expected, to approach the required evacuation time)
- Mobile solution required, that is certified within the limits of normal transport
 - Trailer width < 255 cm width
 - Total mass < 50 ton
- Safe and reliable operation
- Limited noise exposure to the environment

3.2 Compressor types

Several investigations on hydrogen compression can be found in public sources. For example, the extensive but generic handbook “Machinery and Energy Systems for the Hydrogen Economy” [2]. The European Forum for Reciprocating Compressors (EFRC) published a whitepaper, more specifically on hydrogen compression techniques [3]. Within the recent research program HyTros, an investigation was made on offshore hydrogen production & compression [4]. In all these documents, the specific use case of re-compression was not considered. Figure 3-1 represents the compressor map along the axes of capacity (horizontal) and end pressure (vertical), in which a collection of known industrial cases was plotted, for various compressor types. This picture clearly indicates which type of machinery is typically mobilized for which type of compression process. Reciprocating compressors are applied from low to high capacity, up to discharge pressures of 300 bar. For higher discharge pressures, special designs of the reciprocating compressor are used (diaphragm, hydraulic or ionic compressors). Screw compressors are found relatively scarcely for pure hydrogen; these have a broad range of capacity but are limited to discharge pressures of ≈30 bar. Centrifugal compressors are even more rare, for pure hydrogen. If slightly higher molecular weights (MW>3) would be included in the overview, examples of centrifugal compressors would be found. However, these are generally restricted to (very) high capacity and limited discharge pressures and pressure ratios.

Figure 3-1. Compressor map, with indication of industrial use cases for pure hydrogen, for different compression techniques [3].

In the sections below, the main features of the candidate compression techniques are discussed. First, a general description of the compression mechanisms and compressor design are presented (the reader familiar to compressor technology may want to skip this section and move to section 3.3). Next, the specific challenges for the use case of hydrogen re-compression are discussed. Finally, the main pro's and con's of the various compression techniques will be summarized, leading to the conclusion of the most promising concept.

3.2.1 Reciprocating compressor

Reciprocating compressors use the positive displacement principle to increase the pressure of a gas. Via a crank shaft and cross-head mechanism, the rotating motion of the shaft is converted into a reciprocating motion of the piston within the cylinder. Thus, mechanical energy is converted into work on the gas volume inside the cylinder.

Figure 3-2. Schematic overview of a reciprocating compressor cylinder.

The piston reduces the volume of the trapped gas volume, increasing the pressure. This compression process is (approximately) adiabatic, associated with a temperature increase. Inflow into and outflow out of the working chamber is regulated with compressor valves. These valves are spring-loaded, passive devices (plates, rings, poppets) that open once sufficient differential pressure is achieved. The most common arrangement of a piston within a cylinder allows for a double-acting compression mechanism: compression takes places on both sides of the piston (crank-end and head-end side). To limit the temperature increase of the cylinder, due to compression, the cylinders are water-cooled or air-cooled. In case of a horizontal cylinder arrangement, the inflow is usually at the top of the cylinder, the outflow at the bottom of the cylinder. This layout is more favourable to minimize the risk of liquid accumulation inside the cylinder. Ingestion of large liquid slugs into a cylinder is a severe integrity risk and shall be avoided. Lubricated cylinders are most common in industry, which limit the wear of piston rings. For high-speed compressors, lubrication is generally mandatory. Applications that require extreme gas purity, lubrication shall be avoided.

The duty of reciprocating compressors can be characterized over a large range of capacity and pressures (see Figure 3-1). For heavy-duty industrial applications, the design of reciprocating compressors is often dictated by the API 618 standard [5].

As the discharge temperature of the gas shall be controlled to a maximum value, the pressure ratio for each stage is limited. It is limited by a maximum discharge gas temperature, typically 100-150°C, for heavy-duty compressors, designed according to the API 618 standard. The pressure ratio per stage for a reciprocating compressor is typically between 2 and 4, depending on the gas properties and the maximum allowable discharge temperature. To achieve a significant total compression ratio, the design requires several compressor stages. Between each compressor stage, an interstage cooler is applied, usually followed by a separator (knock-out drum, scrubber) before the gas enters the next stage. The individual stages are normally mounted on a single crank shaft, which can accommodate up

to 6 to 8 “throws”³. The advantage of having multiple, even-numbered throws on a single reciprocating compressor is the improved balancing of dynamic forces. For applications mounted on a flexible basis, this is an important aspect to the design (for example on an offshore platform or a trailer).

A very valuable feature of the reciprocating compressor is its versatility with respect to changing process conditions. For example, changes in the inlet/outlet pressures and the gas composition have a limited impact on the compressor efficiency. In other types of compression, such as centrifugal compressors, this is fundamentally different. Also the ability for efficient capacity control is a strong point of the reciprocating compressor. In addition to variable compressor speed, also suction valve unloading, and reverse-flow capacity control are control techniques that have been proven reliable and efficient for many decades.

An intrinsic feature of the reciprocating compressor is that it delivers pulsating (unsteady) flow, due to the reciprocating motion and the action of the compressor valves. For a double-acting cylinder, two pulses occur per revolution of the shaft, alternating by 180 degrees. In case of a single-acting cylinder, the typical dominant pulsation frequency is 1x the compressor running speed. Both at the suction side as at the discharge side, the pulsating flow will lead to pressure fluctuations in the system that propagate in the upstream and downstream directions at the speed-of-sound. To limit the exposure of the pulsations on the pipe system, reciprocating compressors are typically mounted with pulsation dampers at the inlet and outlet of each cylinder. Design of such pulsation dampers is stipulated in industrial standards, such as the American API 618 and API 688.

For pure hydrogen compression, the reciprocating compressor has been the most robust solution in industry for the past decades. This is observed for example in petrochemical plants (refineries) and in the production of green hydrogen with electrolyzers. Compression of (high-purity) hydrogen is normally achieved with multi-stage reciprocating compressors. Inlet pressures range from atmospheric to 30 bar, while discharge pressures range from 40 up to 200 bar, depending on the specific process.

Typical challenges for hydrogen services that are encountered in reciprocating compressor systems:

- A lower outlet temperature is stipulated in the API 618 standard for hydrogen-rich mixtures. This requirement limits the allowable pressure ratio per stage and may lead to more compression stages in the design for large pressure ratios.
- The large range of explosion hazard and the low ignition energy for hydrogen, requires special designs of the cylinder and distance pieces. The leakage from the cylinder into the compressor frame shall be minimized by sufficient gas barriers (packings) and/or nitrogen purging of the crank case.

³ A “throw” in reciprocating compressors refers to the complete assembly including the crankpin on the crankshaft, the connecting rod, the crosshead, and the piston and piston-rod assembly.

3.2.2 Screw compressor

The screw compressor is a special type of positive displacement machine that increases gas pressure by reducing the volume of the trapped gas as it moves through two intermeshing rotating screws, see Figure 3-3 for a schematic overview.

Figure 3-3. Schematic overview of a screw compressor.

These screws consist of a male and a female rotor that rotate in opposite directions. As they turn, gas is drawn into the compression chamber and progressively compressed as the volume between the rotors and the casing decreases. The compressed gas is then discharged through the outlet port. Screw compressors are suitable for the medium to large flow rate range but have limitations on discharge pressure and discharge-to-suction pressure differential. For heavy-duty industrial applications, the design of screw compressors is often dictated by the API 619 standard [6].

Screw compressors are generally categorized into two types: oil-flooded and oil-free, based on whether a lubricant is introduced into the compression chamber. In oil-flooded compressors, the male rotor directly drives the female rotor, and the injected oil must be separated from the compressed gas before it is suitable for downstream use. In contrast, oil-free screw compressors use external timing gears to synchronize the rotors without contact. For applications involving pure hydrogen, where oil contamination must be avoided, oil-free screw compressors are preferred (then often replaced by a water-injected design). The water injection enables to minimize leakages and to control the temperature rise upon compression.

Hydrogen applications face several challenges when using screw compressors. The key issue is managing the losses due to internal clearances, leading to reduced efficiency and limited pressure difference. In partial load operation, the increasing backflow raises the temperature of the machine and the materials, and therefore limits further pressure rise and turn down capability. Additionally, the low molecular weight of hydrogen results in higher optimum compressor tip speeds, which is challenging for fluid injected systems, and creates more heat and wear on the compressor rotors.

In general, screw compressors are -like reciprocating compressors- sources of pulsations. However, screw compressor pulsations occur at high frequency. This is a consequence of the increased rotational

speed, typically ranging from 3000 up to 7000 RPM. The peak pulsations are normally observed at the Pocket-Passing-Frequency (PPF), which is the rotation speed multiplied by the number of male rotor lobes. Usually the male rotor has 4 lobes, so the orders $1xPPF = RPM/60 \times 4$, $2xPPF = RPM/60 \times 8$, etcetera will be found in the pulsation spectrum. These orders can range from several hundred Hz up to 1 kHz. Vibrations will be observed at the same high frequencies. In case these frequencies match with structural mode shapes, a significant vibration response can be observed, with fatigue failure as a consequence (high frequency implies a rapid accumulation of fatigue cycles). At these high frequencies, not only mechanical *bending* modes are efficiently triggered (as for reciprocating compressors) but also *shell* modes along the circumference of the pipe wall. This excitation of shell modes may lead to efficient triggering of small-branch connections (SBCs) and to efficient noise radiation.

The use case of hydrogen re-compression would be in particular unfavourable for a screw compressor, due to the constantly changing pressure differential over the compressor. A screw compressor has an optimal built-in pressure ratio. If the external system pressures are compatible with the built-in internal pressure ratio, the compressor efficiency is optimal and the effect of pulsations minimal. In case of a mismatch between internal and external compression ratio, the efficiency will be less and the pulsation effects will be more severe. Control of these pulsations may involve complex pulsation silencers, including absorption material.

For hydrogen re-compression, the effect of the water injection will be that the design shall have a water supply system and shall include separation of liquids downstream the compressor, which adds to the complexity.

The use case of hydrogen re-compression will require discharge pressures that reach up to 67 bar(a). There are no examples of screw compressors reaching these high-end pressures.

3.2.3 Centrifugal compressor

Centrifugal compressors are widely used in pipeline applications for natural gas. For example, to boost the gas pressure to maintain the required pressures in pipeline systems (both onshore and offshore). In re-compression systems for natural gas, centrifugal compressors are not found.

Figure 3-4. Schematic overview of a centrifugal compressor stage.

A centrifugal compressor increases the pressure by adding kinetic energy to the gas (acceleration). The machine consists of a rotating shaft on which the impellers are placed. The inlet is located close to the shaft, and the gas is flung outwards by rotational forces created by the rotating impeller. As the fluid exits the impeller, it enters a diffuser where the kinetic energy is transferred into static pressure. A single centrifugal compressor can house multiple impellers, also called stages, increasing the pressure each step. The design of these impellers and the required number depends on the required pressure increase. The typical operating conditions for a centrifugal compressors are high capacity at a limited pressure ratio. For heavy-duty industrial applications, the design of centrifugal compressors is often dictated by the API 617 standard [7].

For hydrogen applications, specific challenges arise for the compressor design. Due to the low molecular weight of hydrogen, higher tip speeds (rotational speed of the impeller) are required to achieve the same pressure increase. However, high rotational speeds result in high stresses in the impeller. The limitations of the rotational speed depend on the material choice of the impellers. For tip speeds above 400 m/s only special high-strength alloys are suitable, and above 700 m/s advanced composites are required. These advanced materials are not yet widely applied in high-speed centrifugal compressors. For high-speed applications titanium alloys are frequently used, due to their favourable strength-to-density ratio. However, titanium alloys are especially prone to hydrogen-assisted stress cracking, reducing the reliability.

While a centrifugal compressor is suited for compressing high volumes, the flexibility of the compressor might be a challenge (fluctuating pressure operating conditions). The effectiveness of the centrifugal compressor can decrease for smaller compressed volumes. Also, a minimum flow is required to keep the compressor running within its stable operating envelope (safeguarded by a recycle line). Finally it is preferred that a centrifugal compressor is not used in intermittently as this would lead to higher maintenance cost in the long term.

3.2.4 Non-mechanical compressors

In addition to the traditional mechanical compressor types described above also alternative principles are found. The non-mechanical compressors have limited capacity and have a lower technical readiness level. The most common types of these novel compression technologies are the electrochemical operating principle, the metal-hydrate principle and the adsorption-desorption compression.

Electrochemical compressor

Energy input: electrical

1. Low-pressure anode
2. High-pressure cathode
3. Proton-exchange membrane

Metal hydrides

Energy input: thermal

1. Metal hydride container
2. Cooling (e.g. water)
3. Heating (e.g. waste heat)

Adsorption-desorption

Energy input: thermal

1. High-pressure container
2. Cooling (liquid N₂)
3. Heating (e.g. hot gas)

Figure 3-5. Examples of non-mechanical compression techniques.

Electrochemical compression (also known as electrochemical pumping) is based on the principle of electrochemical dissociation and recombination of hydrogen. An electrochemical compressor is comprised of three main elements:

- **Anode.** In the anode the hydrogen gas is dissociated into protons and electrons.
- **Electrolyte** (typically a proton-conducting membrane). The electrolyte conducts the protons from the anode to the cathode.
- **Cathode.** In the cathode the protons are recombined with the electrons to produce hydrogen gas.

What makes this process a compression process is that, since anode and cathode are separate compartments (separated by the proton-conducting membrane), the cathode can be put under pressure via e.g., flow restriction, whereby the discharge pressure can be increased. This happens because the flow of protons from anode to cathode is not driven by pressure but by electricity flow.

Metal-hydrate and adsorption-desorption are batch-wise processes that use temperature cycles in combination with porous adsorbents.

The scalability of these non-mechanical techniques can be ensured with application of multiple parallel stacks/units. In general, the capacity per stack is limited, for example 10 kg/day (typical for electrochemical units). Mobilization of many parallel stacks on a trailer will lead to heavy demands on terms of footprint and weight.

Promising and powerful features are the fact that non-mechanical technologies has no moving parts. Moreover, the principles are very smooth, silent and void of pulsation and vibration issues.

3.3 Pro-cons for the recompression use case

The advantages and disadvantages of the different compressor techniques are judged, for the use case of hydrogen re-compression. Thereby, the following criteria were considered (in arbitrary order):

- Safety (e.g. explosion)
- Flexibility (range)
- Efficiency (TCO)
- Pulsations, vibrations, noise
- Maturity or Technical Readiness Level (TRL)
- End user experience (maintain)
- Footprint (CSR)
- Hydrogen Purity

The **reciprocating compressor** has the following features:

- Pro:
 - Flexible (high efficiency over full range of inlet/outlet pressure and molecular weights)
 - Medium/large capacity
 - Robust technology
 - Allows for clear compression (non-lube) up to considerable pressures⁴.
 - 50+ years of track record in pure hydrogen compression
 - 20+ years of track record in mobile recompression units
- Con:
 - Vibrations, due to pulsation effects and free forces & moments due to rotating masses
 - Large footprint
 - Lubricated solution

The **high-pressure/low-capacity reciprocating compressors** (diaphragm, hydraulic, ionic) have the following features:

- Pro:
 - Very high discharge pressure (not required for recompression case)
 - High gas purity (not required for recompression case)
 - Mature technology
- Con:
 - Low capacity
 - No track record in large scale, mobile applications
 - Design challenges with intermittent service

The **screw compressor** has the following features:

- Pro:
 - Flexible (high efficiency over a partial range of inlet/outlet pressure)
 - Robust technology (for heavier gases)
 - Compact layout

⁴ In principle up to pressures, sufficient for re-compression purposes. Nevertheless, compressor OEMs often favour a lubricated design.

- Con:
 - Limited discharge pressure to ≈ 30 bar
 - Limited track record with pure hydrogen compression
 - H₂ application requires water injection and post-treatment.
 - No track record in large scale, mobile applications
 - Pulsation, vibrations, noise in particular at variable pressure conditions

The **centrifugal compressor** has the following features:

- Pro:
 - Very high capacity
 - Robust technology (for heavier gases), low maintenance
 - Very compact layout
 - Relatively clean gas service
 - Low pulsations and mechanical vibrations
- Con:
 - Limited flexibility (changes in inlet/outlet pressure)
 - No track record in pure hydrogen compression
 - Fundamental limitation of Δp per stage. For benchmark, 4 stages with 5 wheels/stage would be required (typical $n_{\text{stage}}=1.2$)
 - Increased tip speed and special impeller materials required
 - No track record with mobile recompression applications
 - Noise, high-cycle fatigue issues.

The **non-mechanical compressors** have the following features:

- Pro:
 - Clean
 - Silent, no pulsations or vibrations
 - Low-maintenance
- Con:
 - Very low capacity
 - Batchwise process (metal-hydrate, adsorption/desorption)
 - Low TRL
 - No track record on industrial scale
 - No track record on mobile recompression applications

In a visual overview, the key candidates are judged as follows (+ indicating a positive judgment, - a negative judgement):

Table 3-1. Overall judgement of compression techniques, for the specific use case of mobile recompression.

Criterion	Recip	Screw	Centrif	HP	Non-mech
Flexibility, efficiency in varying pressure conditions	++	+ / -	--	++	++
Capacity	+	+	++	-	--
End pressure / Pressure ratio	+	--	--	+	+
Wear parts, time between maintenance	-	+	+	-	+
Track record, experience	++	-	--	+	-
Footprint	-	+ / -	+	-	+ / -
Gas cleanliness	+ / -	-	+	++	++
Pulsations, vibration, noise	-	+ / -	+	-	++

As indicated with the bold green colours, the most relevant features are optimal in case of the reciprocating compressor. Of all candidates, the reciprocating compressor is judged to have the most favourable combination of features.

3.4 Hybrid compression options

The preferred concept of a mobile recompression unit is a **simple** design, limiting the complexity as much as possible. The ultimate goal to realize a concept that meets the benchmark **into a single trailer**. Reviewing the features of the various compressor types, it was concluded that the reciprocating compressor is the most complete. One of the challenges with a reciprocating compressor is that for low inlet pressures, large cylinder diameters are required. The limitation by footprint will become a challenge for low pressures (typically < 5 bar).

In this low-pressure regime, the screw compressor may be a suitable candidate to act as a booster for the reciprocating compressor. In this way, a hybrid compression solution may be considered. In the current generation green hydrogen plants, that produce at atmospheric conditions (typical for alkaline water electrolysis), such screw + reciprocating compressor combinations are sometimes observed. Though attractive in theory, the system integration of a screw compressor with a reciprocating compressor is obviously much more challenging. The screw compressor is only valid to be used at the end of the evacuation (not at the start, as the inlet/outlet pressures are too high). Hence, a multi-purpose interconnecting piping is required, with pressure relief functionality. The screw compressor requires a water injection system at the inlet, and a post-treatment at the outlet. Liquid management is essential to safeguard the reciprocating compressor from excessive liquid ingestion. Also the driver solution for the two machines is very different (as they run at very different running speeds). It is practically impossible to conceive such a hybrid installation on a single trailer.

In conclusion, a single-type compressor solution is preferred, where the reciprocating compressor is deemed the most suitable candidate. Ideally, a multi-stage configuration is designed that can be fit onto a single trailer. In the next chapter, the feasibility for such 'ideal arrangement' will be investigated.

4. Compressor sizing of the most promising concept

4.1 Compressor performance evaluation

4.1.1 Introduction

The compressor selection analysis as presented in Chapter 3 of this report shows that the most likely compressor concept to evacuate hydrogen, is a reciprocating i.e. piston compressor. In the initial phase of the evacuation this compressor is operated in a 1-stage mode and, as the pressure ratio that needs to be overcome increases, it is switched to a 2-stage, 3-stage, etc. mode configuration. As a driver an E-motor has been selected, as in such a case the flexibility to select an electric power source can be adjusted to more-sustainable technologies as they become available in the course of time. In this paragraph the results of a high-level compressor performance analysis are presented.

4.1.2 Detailed description worst-case design scenario

As a design case for this multi-stage reciprocating compressor concept, Gasunie has defined a worst-case evacuation scenario for the Re-Compression Unit (RCU). The base case parameters have been specified in Table 4-1.

Table 4-1. Description worst-case design evacuation scenario.

Quantity and [unit]	Value	Remark
Pipeline length [km]	80.0	From description Work package WP5b
Outer diameter [inch]	48.0	From description Work package WP5b
Wall thickness [mm]	18.3	Specified by DNV 25/09/19
Pressure in the to-be-evacuated pipe at the start of the evacuation AND in the pipe to which the hydrogen is evacuated [bar(a)]	67.2 57.1	From description Work package WP5b This 15% lower alternative in both pipes is also considered
Pressure in the to-be-evacuated pipe at the end of the evacuation [bar(a)]	1.5	'Preferable' (from Work package WP5b)
Max. suction temperature 1 st stage [°C]	15, 40	Both scenarios are considered
Max. suction temperature higher stages [°C]	15, 40	Both scenarios are considered
Evacuation time [hours]	500	Nearly three weeks
RCU should fit on one standard trailer with a maximum width of 2.55m	-	This requirement was added to the evacuation scenario at the beginning of the project.

Table 4-1 specifies quite an ambitious evacuation scenario in which an 80km-long, large diameter pipeline needs to be evacuated in 500 hours from a starting pressure of 67.2 bar(a) to a final pressure in the to-be-evacuated pipe at the end of the evacuation of 1.5 bar(a) only. This means that in the final stage of the evacuation, the total pressure ratio that the compressor needs to overcome is 44.8 (67.2/1.5).

Note that at the start of the project it has been recognised that this is quite an extreme benchmark. As an alternative, a (slightly) more practical benchmark was defined in which the pressure in the to-be-evacuated pipe and in the pipe section towards which is evacuated, is reduced prior to the start of the evacuation with 15% (57.1 bar(a)). This lower pressure obviously also reduces the maximum pressure ratio that the compressor needs to overcome in the final stage of the evacuation with 15% to 38.1.

As quality of the hydrogen gas the two compositions as listed in Table 4-2 have been specified.

Table 4-2. Hydrogen gas compositions.

Component	Mole percentage	
	Comp. no.1	Comp. no.2
H ₂ – Hydrogen	99.50	98.00
N ₂ – Nitrogen	0.25	1.00
CH ₄ – Methane	0.25	1.00
Mole weight [g/mol]	2.12	2.42

Table 4-2 shows that two compositions have been provided. The first composition consist of 99.5% hydrogen and further contains 0.5% contaminations equally divided over nitrogen and methane. A similar second composition has been specified in which the two contaminations are increased to 1%. Note that for the design and sizing of a piston compressor there is hardly any difference between these two compositions. In the remainder of this section, only composition no.1 has therefore been used as input.

In Table 4-3 some derived quantities are presented that have been used in the initial piston compressor sizing.

Table 4-3. Derived quantities.

Description	Value	Remark
Pipeline volume [m ³]	87873	
Start density [kg/m ³]	5.701	At 15°C and 67.2 bar(a) (RKS Equation-of-State)
Hydrogen mass [tonnes]	501.0	At 67.2 bar(a) start pressure
	425.8	At 57.1 bar(a) start pressure
Average polytropic exponent	1.44	gamma

Table 4-3 shows that at the maximum starting pressure of 67.2bar, more than half a million kilograms (>500 tonnes) of hydrogen gas (composition no.1, in Table 4-2) are present in the to-be-evacuated pipe. In case this pressure is reduced to the specified 1.5bar(a), then 11.2 tonnes or 2.2% will remain in the to-be-evacuated pipe section after the evacuation has been finalised.

4.1.3 Required number of compressor stages

One of the largest challenges in this evacuation benchmark is the large pressure ratio (max. 44.8) that the compressor needs to overcome in the final stage of the evacuation as this will be a measure of how many compressor stages -as a minimum- will be required to reach the end pressure of 1.5 bar(a). Another parameter that affects this minimum required number of stages is the maximum allowable discharge temperature of the hydrogen gas.

This temperature effect is illustrated in Figure 4-1, in which the minimum number of required compressor stages as function of the maximum allowable discharge temperature is plotted. The results are presented for a 15°C and 40°C suction temperature (for all stages) and a final discharge pressure of 67.2 and 57.1 bar(a) (-15% case). This is the pressure in the receiving pipe section towards which the hydrogen is evacuated.

Figure 4-1. Minimum required number of compressor stages as function of maximum allowable discharge temperature.

Figure 4-1 shows that for a maximum allowable discharge temperature of, for instance, 135°C, at least 3 stages will be required when the suction temperature is low (15°C) and at least 4 stages, when the suction temperature of the hydrogen is high (40°C). The plot also shows that the number of minimum required compressor stages is reduced to 2 in case the maximum allowable discharge temperature could be increased to 200°C. This minimum number of required compressor stages in the final stage of the evacuation has a large effect on the complexity of the design of the RCU. For reference, the new natural gas RCUs that will be delivered to Gasunie in 2026/2027 for the evacuation of natural gas, can as a maximum be operated in a 3-stage mode.

Note that Figure 4-1 has been made without taken into consideration any thermodynamic or mechanical losses. This means that the presented number of stages in Figure 4-1 should be regarded as a best-case scenario. When these losses are taken into account it is expected that at least one additional stage will be required, which would result into a minimum of 5 or 3 compressor stages for a maximum allowable discharge temperature of 135°C and 200°C, respectively (taking the higher discharge pressure in the pipe to which the gas is evacuated (67.2 bar(a))).

4.1.4 Maximum allowable discharge temperature

The discharge temperature that as a maximum will be allowed will depend on the type of compressor that will be used and is also a subject of a current debate within the hydrogen compression industry. In section 6.5 of the latest edition of the latest API-Standard 618 [5] it is recommended not to exceed 120°C for 'hydrogen-rich' services (gasses with a mole weight below 12 g/mol). In the previous 5th edition of this standard (December 2007), this maximum recommended temperature was still 135°C.

Note that these recommended temperatures are intended for compressors in which the required uptime is close to 100% and therefore the amount of time that can be spent on maintenance is limited. For the (hydrogen) RCUs the opposite is true: the expected number of times that these compressors are deployed in a year, is small (<20) and therefore also the number of required running hours per year will be much lower. Between deployments, sufficient time should be available for an above-average maintenance scheme.

A second aspect that will affect the maximum allowable discharge temperature (and therefore the minimum required number of compressor stages) will be the presence of lubrication and cooling of the compressor cylinders. In case of lubricated and water-cooled cylinders (or cylinder heads), the general consensus is to allow for higher discharge gas temperatures (even up to 200°C). A higher allowed discharge temperature will reduce the minimum number of required compressor stages. This will thereby greatly simplify the compressor system design and increase the chance that the hydrogen RCU can be fitted on one 'standard' trailer.

The temperatures discussed in this sections are the hydrogen gas temperatures at the discharge (outlet) of the cylinder, immediately after compression. After this compression the gas will be cooled in an interstage or a final discharge cooler. The maximum allowed gas temperature when it is injected into the receiving Gasunie pipe (to which the hydrogen is injected) is 50°C.

4.1.5 Ideal compressor designs

As a next step in the compressor performance evaluation, the benchmark evacuation scenarios that are listed in Table 4-1, have been taken to derive two 'ideal' compressor designs. The main objective of this step in the analysis is to determine how a hydrogen RCU could look like. In these designs no thermodynamic or mechanical losses have been taken into account and also the cylinder bore sizing has been done in such a way that the volume ratios between the different compressor stages in the final stage of the evacuation are optimal (or near optimal).

As starting point a 4-stage compressor with a maximum compressor speed of 1200 RPM has been assumed which services the original benchmark evacuation scenario of Table 4-1. In this scenario the hydrogen is evacuated from the 80km-long, 48" pipe section with a starting pressure of 67.2 bar(a) in the to-be-evacuated pipe and in the pipe towards the hydrogen is evacuated. The final pressure in the to-be-evacuated pipe is 1.5 bar(a) that needs to be reached after 500 evacuation hours (nearly 3 weeks).

The only difference between the two presented designs is the suction (inlet) temperature of the hydrogen. In design no.1 (D1), a suction temperature of 15°C has been taken for all compressor stages. In design no.2 (D2), the suction temperature of the higher stages (2nd, 3rd and 4th) has been increased to 40°C. This latter case is a more realistic representation of the situation in which the evacuation is done at high ambient temperatures, when the interstage cooling is only able to reduce the hydrogen back to a suction temperature (for the next stage) of 40°C.

In Figure 4-2 and Figure 4-3 the evaluation of the 1st stage suction pressure as function of time is plotted by the blue lines. This is the pressure in the to-be-evacuated pipe. The green lines in these figures show the corresponding density of the hydrogen (gas composition no.1 in Table 4-2). This value can be read on the right Y-axis. The purple line in Figure 4-2 and Figure 4-3 indicate the number of stages in which the gas is compressed (right Y-axis). This line indicates the times at which the compressor is (automatically) switched from 1 to 2, from 2 to 3 and from 3 to 4-stage mode operation.

Figure 4-2. Ideal compressor Design no.1: Suction pressure (blue line), density (green line) and number of stages (purple line) as function of evacuation time.

Figure 4-3. Ideal compressor Design no.2: Suction pressure (blue line), density (green line) and number of stages (purple line) as function of evacuation time.

The selected 4-stage compressor concept has 4 double acting (DA) cylinders. In the beginning of the evacuation all cylinders are operated in parallel. After approximately 100 hours of 1-stage operation, the compressor is switched to a 2-stage operation in which cylinder no.1 and no.3 service the 1st stage and cylinder no.2 and no.4 service the 2nd stage. At approximately 220 hours into the evacuation, the compressor is then switched to a 3-stage mode, in which (ideally) cylinder no.1 and no.4 service the 1st stage, cylinder no.2 the 2nd stage, and cylinder no.3 the 3rd stage. In the final stage of the operation, the compressor is operated in a four-stage mode, in which each cylinder number services the corresponding stage (cylinder no.1 the 1st stage, cylinder no.2 the 2nd stage, etc.). The cylinder stroke has been selected as 50% of the bore of the largest cylinder (cylinder that services the first stage in the final part of the evacuation). The bores of the smaller cylinders have been based on ideal volume ratios over the stages. In this way no valve unloaders (or other forms of capacity control over the cylinders and stages) would be required. For design no.2, a fixed correction factor is used to compensate for the higher maximum suction temperature for the higher stages (40°C versus 15°C).

In Figure 4-4 and Figure 4-5 the estimated discharge temperatures as function of time are plotted. From Figure 4-4 it can be seen that for design no.1 (D1) the maximum temperatures are -as expected- reached when the cylinders are operating at a maximum pressure ratio. Figure 4-4 shows that these maximum temperatures remain below 120°C throughout the evacuation. As within D1 the assumed suction temperature is 15°C for all stages, the predicted discharge temperatures are identical for all stages in the later phases of the evacuation (during the 2-stage, 3-stage and 4-stage operating modes).

Figure 4-4. Ideal compressor Design no.1: Discharge temperature 1st stage (yellow line) and 2nd, 3rd and 4th stage (red line) and number of stages (purple line) as function of evacuation time.

In Figure 4-5 the discharge temperatures are plotted for D2 in which the assumed suction temperature for the higher stages is increased to 40°C. This change obviously also increases the discharge temperatures. The yellow line in Figure 4-5 represents the discharge temperature of the hydrogen gas of stage 1, while the red line indicates the discharge temperatures for the 2nd, 3rd and 4th stage. The maximum temperature in Figure 4-5 is 138°C.

Figure 4-5. Ideal compressor Design no.2: Discharge temperature 1st stage (yellow line) and 2nd, 3rd and 4th stage (red line) and number of stages (purple line) as function of evacuation time.

In Figure 4-6 and Figure 4-7 the compressor mass flowrate and consumed (adiabatic) power is plotted as function of evacuation time. These plots indicate that -as expected- at the start of the evacuation this mass flowrate (blue line) is the highest and as the evacuation progresses, less and less hydrogen is evacuated. A significant portion of the evacuation time is required to compress relatively small amounts of hydrogen ('long tail'). In the final (500th) hour of the evacuation, less than 100kg of hydrogen gas is recovered.

The green lines in Figure 4-6 and Figure 4-7 indicate the consumed adiabatic compression power as function of time. These plots indicate that the maximum power consumption occurs just before the compressor is switched from a 1-stage to a 2-stage mode. For these 'ideal' compressors, these peaks in the power consumption are approximately 700 and 750kW for design no.1 and design no.2, respectively. The plots indicate that due to the higher suction temperatures for the higher stages in design no.2, a slightly larger compressor will be needed to complete the benchmark evacuation of Table 4-1 within 500 hours.

Figure 4-6. Ideal compressor Design no.1: Mass flowrate of the evacuated hydrogen (blue line) and consumed adiabatic compression power (green line) as function of evacuation time.

Figure 4-7. Ideal compressor Design no.2: Mass flowrate of the evacuated hydrogen (blue line) and consumed adiabatic compression power (green line) as function of evacuation time.

Note that as the compressor will be E-motor driven, it is likely that this motor will be equipped with a variable speed drive (VSD). This VSD can be applied to during starts and stops of the unit (for instance during stage switchovers), but -if required- can also be used as a ‘peak-shaver’ to minimise the peaks in the consumed power of the RCU (at the cost of a longer evacuation time).

In Table 4-4 the basic compressor data are presented of the ideal design no.1 and no.2 compressors. In this table the bores of the four cylinders, the swept volume and the totally consumed compression energy during the evacuation benchmark, are listed.

Table 4-4. Basic compressor data ideal compressor designs no.1 and no.2.

Description	Design 1 (15°C)	Design 2 (15, 40°C)
Number of stages	1 → 2 → 3 → 4	1 → 2 → 3 → 4
Maximum compressor speed [RPM]	1200	1200
Swept volume (1-stage operation) [dm ³ /rev.]	12.3	12.9
Stroke [mm]	109	108
Bores cyl.no 1-4 [mm]	218, 136, 84, 52	216, 152, 89, 53
Peak power [kW]	702	751
Consumed energy [MWh]	159	165
Max. discharge temperature [°C]	113	138

4.1.6 Sensitivity analysis

To better understand the relations between the different parameters, a sensitivity analysis has been added to the compressor performance evaluation. In this section the effect of a longer evacuation time (5 versus 3 weeks), the effect of compressor speed and the effect of the 15% lower pressure in the to-be-evacuated pipe and in the receiving pipe are described:

- The evacuation time is inversely proportional to the power consumption. Increasing the evacuation time from 3 to 5 weeks ($\times 5/3$), reduces the peak power consumption with 40% ($\times 3/5$).
- Increasing the maximum compressor speed from 1200 to 1500 RPM ($\times 5/4$) will reduce the evacuation time with 20% ($\times 4/5$) and will increase the peak power consumption with 25% ($\times 5/4$). The totally consumed (adiabatic) compression energy (≈ 160 MWh) remains constant and is represented by the integrated area underneath the (green) power curve in for instance Figure 4-7.
- Reducing the suction pressure in the to-be-evacuated pipe with 15% (from 67.2 to 57.1 bar(a), only slightly reduces the peak in the power consumption (-2%). A larger reduction of the peak in power consumption (-12%) occurs, in case also the delivery pressure in the receiving pipe section is lowered prior to the start of the evacuation.

4.1.7 Conclusions

- To achieve a total pressure ratio of 44.8 (suction pressure 1.5 bar(a) to final discharge pressure 67.2 bar(a)), at least 4 stages will be required in case the maximum discharge temperature is to remain below 150°C. In case higher cylinder temperatures would be allowed then a 3-stage compressor might suffice.
- The switching from one to the next stage operation will in most cases be governed by the maximum allowable discharge temperature. Note that the negative JT-coefficient of hydrogen only marginally reduces the temperature during compression (compared to ideal gas).
- The required power strongly depends on the stage of the evacuation. In case of a single unit, maximum power will be required at the end of the 1-stage operation. This maximum required power is similar to the power of the current Gasunie RCUs for natural gas.

4.2 Practical feedback from compressor packagers/OEM/End Users

4.2.1 Introduction

As indicated, in the ideal compressor designs as presented in paragraph 4.1, TNO has not taken into account any thermodynamic or mechanical losses. In these designs also the requirement that the compressor should fit on one standard trailer (with a maximum width of 2.55m) or any other dimensional or weight restrictions could not be taken into account. As a next step in the conceptual designs of the hydrogen RCUs, TNO has therefore interviewed several market parties (see paragraph 4.2.5), to review the ideal compressor design and to check what could realistically be fitted on one standard trailer.

All parties have -in different levels of detail- commented to the evacuation benchmark as described in Table 4-1. The most important physical differences that have been identified between the future hydrogen RCUs and existing RCUs for natural gas are:

1. The requirement to apply a **double distance piece** for hydrogen applications.
2. The difference in **system losses and fluid properties** will most likely results in 1 (or even 2) additional compressor stages unless a high discharge temperature would be allowed (see Figure 4-1).

The consequence of the requirement to apply a double distance piece is, that it will not be possible to fit a 6-throw (or 4-throw) boxer-type compressor (with horizontal cylinders on opposite sides of the crankcase) on one trailer with a width below 2.55m. Compressors with even the smallest available frame sizes will exceed this width. The alternative to use only cylinders on one side (and dummy weights on the other) will mean that the maximum number of cylinders is reduced to three, which is less than number of compressor stages that will be required (for this type of compressor). Although technically still possible, this will lead to quite a complex and convoluted design.

Based on the interviews with the market parties the following three compressor concepts have been identified. Please note that none of these three presented concepts meet all the worst-case benchmark criteria of Table 4-1.

4.2.2 Compressor concept 1

The only compressor concept that has been identified that will fit on one standard trailer is a small-sized V-type compressor that is equipped with 4 water-cooled lubricated cylinders. This type of 1200-RPM compressor will be able to operate with high discharge temperatures and will be able to overcome the high required pressure ratio at the final stages of the evacuation in only 3 (or maximum 4) stages. The only parameter where this compressor concept clearly does not meet the benchmark requirements (Table 4-1) will be the evacuation time. In the current RCU market for natural gas, smaller (100kW) units exist which will have less than 10% of the required capacity. This would mean that the required evacuation time is increased to nearly 45(!) weeks. In Figure 4-8 the estimated suction pressure in the to-be-evacuated pipe and adiabatic compressor power as function of evacuation time of such a small compressor unit are plotted.

Figure 4-8. Compressor Concept 1 - Small 4-stage V-type concept with cooled and lubricated cylinders.

The most obvious manner to reduce this very long evacuation time would be to deploy multiple units and to operate them in parallel. To meet the specified evacuation time of 500 hours, an unpractical number of 15 units would in theory be required. As time evolves and the hydrogen recompression market would become more mature, then this compressor concept shall be increased in size. Market parties confirm that 300kW or even 500kW units would likely become available in the future, then the number of required parallel units that can meet the 500 hours evacuation time will roughly be reduced to 5 or 3, respectively.

TNO considers this compressor concept to be the most-likely candidate for the future hydrogen RCUs. Although their capacity may be (far) too small at this point in time, this is likely to be increased in the future, and a big advantage of such a concept is that these units can also easily be deployed for smaller evacuation jobs (which are more likely to occur in a nearer future). A point of attention in the detailed design of this compressor concept will be the higher free forces and moments (compared to a boxer-type compressor). These higher forces and moments need to be carefully considered in the mechanical design of the trailer.

4.2.3 Compressor concept 2

Another already existing compressor concept will be a 6-throw boxer-type compressor. This type of compressor has a larger capacity (and therefore a shorter evacuation time than the 100kW compressor concept no.1). The expected evacuation time will be close to 10 weeks, which will mean that 3 units could be deployed in parallel to bring this time down to (approximately) 3 weeks. In Figure 4-9 the estimated suction pressure in the to-be-evacuated pipe and shaft power curves of such a compressor unit are plotted. In this figure the power curve (green line) is the predicted shaft power, so in this curve the expected thermodynamic and mechanical losses within the compressor systems are taken into account. Figure 4-9 also shows that to simplify the compressor system design, the compressor is selected to only be able to operate in a 1-, 3- and 5-stage mode (and to skip the 2- and 4-stage mode operation).

Figure 4-9. Compressor Concept 2 – Larger 5-stage Boxer-type compressor concept.

The largest drawback is that this 2nd compressor concept does not fit on a standard trailer with a maximum width of 2.55m. This will mean that a special type of (permanent or temporary) permit will be required to be able to transport this trailer on the public road. In extreme cases, it may even mean that certain remote areas may not be accessible at all.

An advantage of this 2nd concept is that the compressor will be located on only one side of the driver, while in concept no.1 the driver is (usually) located in the middle of two V-type compressor units. This latter design will require a more complex ATEX design. Similar as concept no.1, concept no.2 will be easy to deploy for smaller evacuation jobs (which are more likely to occur in a nearer future).

4.2.4 Compressor concept 3

Most contacted market parties agree that the compressor concept that comes closest to the specified long-term benchmark evacuation (80 km; 48 inch in 500 hours) in terms of evacuation time, will be a more complex, multi-trailer concept. This concept consists of (a) high-pressure (HP) compressor(s) and a later added high-capacity low-pressure (LP) booster compressor which both fit on (separate) standard trailers. In Figure 4-10 an example of the power consumption of such a multi-trailer concept with one HP-compressor and one LP-compressor is given. In this figure the power curve (green line) is the predicted shaft power, so in this curve the expected combined thermodynamic and mechanical losses within the compressor systems are taken into account.

Figure 4-10: Compressor Concept 3 – Multi-trailer HP+LP compressor concept, each with 3 cylinders.

Figure 4-10 shows that within this concept, the HP-compressor (with a high design pressure) is operating for more than 4½ weeks. Within this time the HP-compressor is operating in a 1-, 2- and 3-stage mode, respectively. After this 4½ weeks, the LP-compressor (with a lower design pressure) is placed between the HP-compressor and the to-be-evacuated pipe, so that it can function as a booster for the HP-compressor. As the LP-compressor has a lower design pressure, it can be fitted with much larger bore cylinders, which will have a significant reducing effect on the time required during the final stages of the evacuation. In Figure 4-10 this effect can be seen at the knee point in the suction pressure curve (blue line). In the final week of the evacuation, this LP-compressor is operated in a 2-stage and 3-stage mode, so both compressors combined, work in series in a 5-stage and 6-stage mode. Note that in this particular example, the end pressure in the to-be-evacuated pipe is even reduced to 1.2 bar(a) (0.3 bar lower than the specified 1.5 bar(a)). Note that the evacuation time could be reduced to less than 500 hours, by starting the evacuation with two parallel HP-compressors, which are later accompanied by one LP-compressor.

In Figure 4-10 a second peak in the power consumption occurs when the LP compressor starts operating (after approximately 4½ weeks). As the compressors will be E-motor driven, this 2nd peak in the power consumption can be reduced by temporarily reducing the speed. This will however increase the evacuation time.

This HP+LP concept obviously does not meet the requirement that the complete RCU concept should fit on one trailer. This quite complex concept will also reduce flexibility and will be less practical for smaller evacuation deployments.

4.2.5 Overview of contacted market parties

- ConPackSys, Dordrecht, Netherlands
- PEB, Zoetermeer, Netherlands
- Leobersdorfer Maschinen Fabrik (LMF), Leobersdorf, Austria
- Compressor Systems Holland (HCS), Vianen, Netherlands
- NEA, Übach-Palenberg, Germany
- Howden, Rheden, Netherlands

4.2.6 Miscellaneous topics

In this section a short overview is presented of several topics that have been discussed during progress meetings and during the interviews with the market parties. These topics have been added to this report, as they could also affect the choice of the hydrogen RCU compressor concept.

- The E-motor driver of the compressor is likely to be equipped with a Variable Speed Drive (VSD). If desired this VSD can be used for peak-shaving of the power curve. This will obviously increase the evacuation time.
- To allow for a higher discharge temperature, the cylinders are likely to be lubricated. This will add a little amount of lubrication oil to the hydrogen gas. To remove most of this oil, a small coalescing filter will need to be added in the final discharge to the compressor system design. Note that the cylinders of the (much larger) compressors that will be used in the hydrogen storage (HyStock) that is planned to be built in Zuidwending, are also lubricated.
- In the current design of the new RCUs for natural gas, the vent gas of the compressor is fed to the gas- or diesel engine that drives the generator set. In case for the hydrogen RCUs a different type of driver (or electricity source) would be selected, then this gas (mixture of hydrogen and nitrogen) will need to be compressed back into the hydrogen system or flared. The use of a vent stack (without ignition) is not recommended, due to the high risk on autoignition of the hydrogen.
- Most contacted market parties expect that the reciprocating compressors will need to be placed in a noise enclosure to reduce the noise emissions of the installation (similar to the current RCUs). The increased explosion risk of hydrogen (compared to natural gas) is expected to be sufficiently mitigated by increasing the ventilation rate in the enclosure and possibly by increasing the number of gas detection sensors.
- In case the cylinders or cylinder heads are water-cooled, then this coolant system could also be extended to cool the hydrogen gas in the compressor's interstages and final discharge. This can make the compressor system less complex, as in such a case only one single air fin cooler can be used to cool the coolant against the ambient air. The second benefit could be the lower suction interstage temperature of the hydrogen that can be reached in this way. A possible drawback of such a cooling system could be the additional weight.

4.3 Conclusions

In this chapter a high-level sizing has been executed for the three most promising reciprocating compressor concepts. Most important conclusion of this evaluation is that none of these three concepts meets the ambitious evacuation benchmark as described in Table 4-1. In TNO's view, the most promising concept will be a smaller V-type compressor that is equipped with 4 water-cooled lubricated double acting (DA) cylinders. This type of 1200-RPM compressor will be able to operate with high discharge temperatures and will be able to achieve the high required pressure ratio at the final stages of the evacuation in only 3 (or maximum 4) stages. The only parameter where this compressor concept clearly does not meet the benchmark requirements, will be the evacuation time. In the current RCU market for natural gas, smaller (100kW) units exist which will have less than 10% of the required capacity. As time evolves and the hydrogen recompression market would become more mature, then this compressor concept is likely to be increased in size. Assuming that 300kW or even 500kW units would become available in the future, then 5 or 3 parallel operated units should be able to meet the 500 hours evacuation time.

TNO considers this compressor concept to be the most-likely candidate for the future hydrogen RCUs. Although their capacity may be (too) small at this point in time, this is likely to be increased in the future. A second advantage of such a concept is that these units can also easily be deployed for smaller evacuation jobs (which are more likely to occur in a nearer future).

A competing concept could be a boxer-type compressor with a larger capacity, but the width of such a compressor will exceed the 2.55m limit, so it will not fit on a standard trailer. This will mean that a special type of (permanent or temporary) permit will be required to be able to transport this trailer on the public road. Also from this type of compressor, 3 units will be required to meet the 500-hour evacuation time.

In case the evacuation time of the benchmark evacuation is the most important parameter, then a multi-trailer concept with one (or two) high-pressure compressors and one large-capacity low-pressure compressor will be the most suitable concept. Also this HP+LP compressor concept obviously does not meet the requirement that the RCU concept should fit on a single trailer. This quite complex concept will also reduce flexibility and will be less practical for smaller evacuation deployments.

5. Driver and power supply options

In this chapter, the options for driving the re-compression units are discussed. Regardless of the type of compressors to be selected, there are basically two ways to power the compression unit, either by a direct, or by an indirect drive. In the former case the drive directly powers the compressor's main shaft, in the latter case the compressor is powered by an electric motor which in its turn is provided with electric power from a separate generator set.

Both options will be further elaborated upon in the next sections.

5.1 Direct drive option

In Gasunie's existing re-compression units, a natural gas engine is applied to directly drive the crankshaft of the 2-cylinder, double action piston compressor. Depending on the compressor's operation mode (cylinders operating in series or parallel), the required compressor power provided by the engine varies in time. This sets certain requirements to the drive's rangeability (50-100%) and may result in the engine having to work outside its operations envelope.

A significant advantage of applying a direct drive is that both the compressor and the engine can be mounted on one trailer, therefore reducing the logistics effort to get the re-compression unit on site. On the other hand, a gas engine occupies much of the available space inside the trailer so that less room remains for the compressor itself, reducing its size and capacity, and sooner leading to situations in which multiple compressor units must be applied in parallel, requiring a higher transport effort. Fuel can be obtained directly from the compressor's suction section, so no separate fuel supply lines need to be added.

Apart from (inter and after) cooling of the compressed gas and the compressor's lubricating oil, in case of a direct drive, also the cooling of water and lubrication oil from the engine is to be done with the trailer's on-board cooling section, which may also take some additional space.

Overall, the biggest advantage of a direct drive is that the trailer can be positioned after arrival and operated with a minimum of connections to auxiliary systems. The recompression unit is virtually self-sufficient when discarding fuel supply. This not only has operational advantages, but lack of cables and pipelines feeding into the unit and crossing the construction site reduces the risk of incidents and accidents happening. However, considering Gasunie's desire to limit greenhouse gas emissions in recompression activities, a direct drive may offer too little options for using various low-emission fuels, and limited flexibility regarding the type of technologies to be applied.

5.2 Indirect drive option

Especially in the transportation sector, so called diesel-electric drives have become quite common over the past decades, e.g. on-board ships and trains. In general, advantages of propulsion systems equipped with diesel-electric drives are:

- Flexibility in placement of the engine (disconnected from the main shaft);
- No gearbox required;
- High torque over entire load range;
- Very low speeds and loads possible, e.g. by applying a load bank.

Disadvantages are

- Relatively high construction costs;
- Complex construction, including electronics;

- Higher fuel consumption due to an additional energy conversion stage.
- Dependent on the availability of a separate (rental) genset

In the indirect case, the additional generation and conversion stage incurs some efficiency loss (roughly 5–10%), whereas the direct drive transmits mechanical power with minimal conversion losses. In the case of Gasunie's hydrogen recompression units, another big advantage is to be mentioned. Once the compressor type and configuration are selected, a suitable electric motor can be picked from a long list of available brands and types, delivering the best performance regarding torque and speed over the whole load range. Based on the motor specifications, the most suitable power generation system can be selected. This also allows for future emissions reduction by renting low carbon gensets as they become available, whereas the direct engine is limited to the current technologies.

Selection of the most suitable electric motor can best be done by the packager who will be responsible for the design and assembly of the re-compression unit.

In this context, it is important to mention that Gasunie has decided to obtain full ownership of the compressor unit, but that a generator set is likely to be hired case-by-case, based on the typical circumstances that may occur per pipeline evacuation job. Besides the powering of the compressor itself, the generator set is also required to deliver power to all kinds of other processes, like lighting the site, driving site dewatering and LIN-pumps (if applicable), power tools, etc.

The choice of the power generator and the applied fuels will then determine the level of harmful emissions (both from a local air quality and global warming perspective). By uncoupling the power generation process from the re-compression itself, a large degree of flexibility is obtained because the most suitable technology/fuel combination may be hired depending on local circumstances like required total power, availability and price of certain fuels and advancing technology development over time. In practice, this means that for each evacuation job a suitable and available genset must be found.

Because of these obvious advantages, Gasunie has decided to opt for the indirect drive concept.

5.3 Conceptual design

In the below diagram, the gen-set/re-compressor configuration is depicted. In the diagram, the gen-set basically consists of an engine and a generator, but instead of a separate drive and generator, a fuel cell delivering the power may also be applied. For practical reasons it is assumed that the gen-set delivers three phase power of 400 V and 50 Hz. Further specifications are to be discussed with the gen-set rental company, e.g. referring to **ISO 8528-1** (Application, rating and performances) and underlying/related standards.

Figure 5-1. Gen-set/re-compressor configuration.

Gensets are to be delivered/mounted on a separate trailer, i.e. in its own enclosure like a (sea)container. The genset needs to be equipped with all necessary provisions like:

- Power quality control systems;
- Safety devices;
- UPC battery;
- Flue gas purification system;
- Fuel supply and power line connectors;
- Dampers and other noise reduction measures.

Further specifications are to be agreed upon between Gasunie and the rental company. In case of external fuel supply, a fuel storage depot is to be established as well honouring safety distances and ATEX zoning to be established during QRAs and other safety assessments.

It is assumed that the re-compression unit will be equipped with a Variable Speed Drive (VSD) also known as Variable Frequency Drive (VFD). Such device allows for the accurate setting of the speed of the motor/compressor combination, by frequency controlling the power supplied by the genset. Although a VSD/VFD comes with a certain loss of energy efficiency, it is recommended to include such device into the design because of its advanced speed control capability.

The main power consumer is the re-compressor itself, but other processes also require electrical power like the fans used in the fin-fan gas chiller and enclosure ventilation, oil and water pumps, control systems and safety devices. The advantage of using an external power supply is that the on-board diesel fuelled genset as applied in the current re-compression units will become superfluous, thus providing additional space and reducing the overall weight of the trailer. It is recommended that each trailer (compressor and generator) must have a UPS backup: the compressor UPS will supply its control and safety circuits to allow a controlled shutdown, and the genset UPS will cover the generator's control/protection systems. This ensures no loss of safety functionality in the event of power interruption.

Apart from the power directly used by the re-compression unit, there may well be other devices on the construction site that require electrical power. On top of the maximum power required for driving the re-compressor and auxiliary systems, the genset capacity is to be based on the total power that may be required at a given time. This needs to be considered on a case-to-case basis, depending on the local situation, and the maximum power taken by the re-compressor itself, but in general, the total power demand will be between 500 and some 800 kVA.

In Figure 5-2, a picture of an 800 kVA rental generator set is shown. As an indication, the specifications of such set are:

Continuous power output	800 kVA
Dimensions (LxWxH)	6.06 x 2.44 x 2.60m
Weight	11,000 kg
Noise level at 7 meters	70 dB (A)
Fuel	Diesel, GTL, HVO biofuel

It may be concluded that regardless of the actual power requirements, a genset suitable for driving the re-compression unit and auxiliary systems will fit on a normal trailer.

Figure 5-2. 800 kVA generator set.

Basically, there are quite a few technology and fuel combinations available for generating power in off-grid situations. Some combinations are commonly used already, and others are still under development, but each combination has its own unique set of performance characteristics. There are three basic technologies for providing power in off-grid situations, being:

- Engine/generator combinations;
- Fuel cells;
- Batteries.

The various technology and fuel combinations will be discussed in more detail in the next section.

5.4 Generator concepts

In the context of this study and in consultation with Gasunie, the feasibility of the following generator concepts was assessed:

- Diesel engine (as the reference).
- Hydrogen engine;
- Bio-CNG engine;
- Natural gas engine;
- Hydrotreated Vegetable Oil (HVO)-engine;
- Bio-methanol engine;

- Ammonia engine;
- Hydrogen fuel cell;
- Battery;

The various technologies, apart from the diesel fuelled generator sets will be discussed in the next paragraphs.

5.4.1 Hydrogen engine

Hydrogen engines are also known as 'H2 ICE' (Hydrogen Internal Combustion Engine) which are basically adapted Otto-cycle engines. Hydrogen combustion in an engine produces water and NO_x (nitrogen oxides) emissions. Compared to other Otto processes like engines running on petrol or gas, several modifications are required. This includes steel that must be resistant to hydrogen embrittlement and higher combustion temperatures, and modifications to the catalyst to reduce NO_x emissions (Alliance Technical Services, 2025). Engine-out NO_x emissions can exceed 10 g/kWh_e without controls [8]. Companies like Jenbacher make engines that work partly (as in; 10-30% H₂ the rest natural gas) or entirely on hydrogen.

Figure 5-3. 100 kVA hydrogen combustion generator (HISIS, 2024).

Currently there are no hydrogen generator sets above 500kW commercially available for hire. For example, Figure 5-3 shows a 100 kVA generator set that runs on hydrogen. In practice, most generators with internal combustion engines are installed in housings.

In Gasunie's case, fuel may be directly supplied from the hydrogen pipeline to be evacuated, or tube trailers can be used. Some basic calculations with:

- Continuous power demand of the re-compressor and auxiliary systems: 500 kWh_e;
- Electric efficiency of the generator set: 40%;

For this, a hydrogen supply of $(500 \text{ kJ/s} / 0.40) = 1250 \text{ kJ/s}$ is required. Considering a Net Calorific Value of hydrogen of 119.96 MJ/kg, a continuous supply of $1.25 / 119.96 = 0.01042 \text{ kg/s}$ or 37.5 kg/h is to be maintained. Given a load capacity of 380 kg for a tube trailer, a new trailer must arrive every 10 hours.

A serious problem with hydrogen-powered generators is that mobile versions with high capacities are currently not offered much, or actually not on a rental basis, in the market. Whether such rental generators indeed will be offered in future will depend on the development of the hydrogen market. Therefore, for the moment, obtainability of such systems is considered rather low.

Table 5-1. Emission levels associated with a hydrogen engine.

Emissions	Unit	Typical value
CO₂ equivalent (WTP)	<i>kg/kWh_e</i>	0.05 (green)
		0.8 (grey)
NO_x (TTP)	<i>g/kWh_e</i>	0.5
Particulate, soot	<i>mg/kWh_e</i>	0
Other		NO _x emissions can exceed diesel NO _x by factor 3 if uncontrolled. Emissions can be cut to 0.5 g/kWh _e by lean burn, EGR, or SCR [9].

5.4.2 Bio-CNG engine

Bio-CNG stands for Compressed Natural Gas of biological origin (bio methane). Bio methane is made by fermenting waste products such as sludge, vegetable waste and manure. In the fermentation process, a carbon-containing waste product (biomass) is converted by bacteria into a natural gas which contains 45-65% methane and a part of CO₂, which can be removed until it is comparable to normal natural gas.

Because the gas is of biological origin, it provides a significant CO₂ reduction compared to fossil natural gas (OG Clean Fuels, 2025). Upgraded biomethane can reduce CO₂ emissions by 60–80% on a well-to-wheel (or well-to-power) basis versus fossil fuels. For instance, Renewable Natural Gas from landfill gas emits 29 g CO₂e/kWh_e versus 234 g CO₂e/kWh_e from natural gas [2]. Moreover, the digested biomass can be used as fertilizer. Modern CNG engines emit very low particulate matter and can meet NO_x limits, but methane slip (unburned CH₄) can occur. Without an oxidation catalyst, a few percent of fuel may pass unburnt, which for a 500 kW genset, the order of 2-20 g CH₄ per kWh_e depending on the (partial) load of the generator [10].

Combustion of CNG in an engine takes place in an Otto process. Companies such as Cummins and Bredenoord offer generator sets that work on (Bio-)CNG. Natural gas generators look similar to the hydrogen generator pictured above. CNG-generator sets are already available in a wide capacity range of up to 9 MW.

In the Gasunie situation, CNG is to be stored on-site. For CNG supply and storage, tube trailers can be applied. In the following example, the logistics involved in CNG supply are assessed.

Some basic calculations:

- Continuous power demand of the re-compressor and auxiliary systems: 500 kWh_e;
- Electric efficiency of the generator set: 40%;

For this, a constant CNG supply of $(500 \text{ kJ/s} / 0.4) = 1250 \text{ kJ/s}$ is required.

Considering a Net Calorific Value of CNG (natural gas) of 37.5 MJ/kg, a continuous supply of $1.25 / 37.5 = 0.033 \text{ kg/s}$ or 120 kg/h is to be maintained. Given a load capacity of 4752 kg (at 250 bar) like in the trailer shown in the picture below, roughly every **40 hours** a new trailer must arrive.

Figure 5-4. Example of a 36-ft tube trailer (250 bar(g), 4752 kg). Source: sinogas.

Some recent developments include the use of tanks made from composite materials which allow for a higher filling pressure (up to 500, and even 750 bar(g)). This would of course extend the time between tube trailer replacements proportionally.

Table 5-2. Emission levels associated with a gas (CNG) engine.

<i>Emissions</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Typical value</i>
CO₂ equivalent (WTP)	<i>kg/kWh_e</i>	-0.2 to 0.4 (depending on origin)
NO_x (TTP)	<i>g/kWh_e</i>	0.5
Particulate, soot	<i>mg/kWh_e</i>	1–5
Other		CH ₄ slip from engine 2-20 g CH ₄ [10]

5.4.3 Natural gas engine

In some cases, a natural gas pipeline may be on, or in close vicinity of the construction site, thus providing an opportunity to tap into the line and use natural gas as a fuel for the generator drive. In such cases no external supply of fuel would be required but depending on the origin of the gas inside the pipeline, there will be more or less CO₂ emissions produced upon use in the generator set drive.

The volume of the fuel gas required is roughly the same as in case of using CNG which amounts at 120 kg/h or some 100 m³(n)/h in case of natural gas of G-gas specifications. In case of H-gas being available on site, fuel requirements will be somewhat less.

Table 5-3 Emission levels associated with a natural gas engine.

<i>Emissions</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Typical value</i>
CO₂ equivalent (WTP)	<i>kg/kWh_e</i>	-0.2 to 0.4 (depending on origin)
NO_x (TTP)	<i>g/kWh_e</i>	0.5
Particulate, soot	<i>mg/kWh_e</i>	1–5
Other		CH ₄ slip from engine 2-20 g CH ₄ [10]

5.4.4 HVO engine

Hydrotreated vegetable oil (HVO) is diesel made from vegetable oils and animal fats such as used frying oil and palm oil and then isomerized (Oftec, 2021). The product is a paraffinic fuel with similar combustion properties to diesel. Its properties are so similar that it is considered a drop-in fuel. This means that an engine designed to run on diesel can run also on HVO and vice versa, without significant technical modifications required.

Its paraffinic composition leads to lower particulate matter (30% less particulate mass), nitrogen (30% less NO_x) and sulphur emissions (near 0) compared to fossil diesel [11]. Because HVO diesel is produced from biomass, the short carbon cycle allows for up to 89% reduction for the net lifecycle CO₂.

HVO supply is limit at scale, but feedstock availability caps growth. HVO fuel also comes at a premium of 10–20% higher cost per liter than diesel

Some basic calculations:

- Continuous power demand of the re-compressor and auxiliary systems: 500 kW_{he};
- Electric efficiency of the generator set: 40%;

For this, a constant HVO supply of (500 kJ/s / 0.4) = 1250 kJ/s is required.

Considering a Calorific Value of HVO of 34 MJ/liter, a continuous supply of 1.25 / 34 = 0,037 liter/s or 133 liter/h is to be maintained. Assuming a storage tank volume of 10 m³, roughly every **75 hours** a new supply of HVO must arrive.

Table 5-4. Emission levels associated with an HVO engine.

Emissions	Unit	Typical value
CO₂ equivalent (WTP)	kg/kWh _e	0.12-0.2 (depended on origin)
NO_x (TTP)	g/kWh _e	0.36 (with SCR)
Particulate, soot	mg/kWh _e	94 (unfiltered, 30% less than diesel) 1 – 10 (with DPF) [12]
Other		

5.4.5 Methanol engine

Methanol (CH₃OH) is an organic compound that is liquid at room temperature and can be used as fuel. Methanol is made from carbon monoxide and hydrogen from natural gas but can also be made from biogas. In addition to being a hydrogen carrier, methanol can also be used directly as a fuel for Otto-cycle engines. Methanol can also be used in a diesel engine by injecting a small amount of diesel (2-20% (Maritime Technology, 2023)) during the engine cycle to ignite the fuel. This is called dual fuel combustion as most methanol engines are developed to also work with fossil diesel. This development stems from shipping. For an Otto-cycle engine, methanol is therefore relatively drop in; diesel engines require modifications, such as a second fuel line and tank and injection systems, among others. The shipping sector, as well as the power generation sector in China, use methanol to generate work and power (Li et al., 2018).

For the current report, the starting point for methanol combustion is that the methanol is burned in a diesel engine by means of a pilot injection of diesel. In the maritime sector, this is one of the most common combustion mechanisms due to the high-power requirements and the relatively high

efficiency of the diesel cycle (MAN, 2021). For methanol there are currently several combustion methods under development, including Otto-cycle engines (Bredenoord).

Given the highly combustible nature of methanol, specific precautions must be taken for on-site storing. Methanol has a lower energy capacity with an NCV 15.65 MJ/l (at 1 atm, 25 °C), that is 40% of diesel’s volumetric energy density, so fuel tanks must be two times larger for the same energy source.

In the Gasunie situation, methanol is to be stored on-site. For CNG supply and storage, tube trailers can be applied. In the following example, the logistics involved in CNG supply are assessed.

Some basic calculations:

- Continuous power demand of the re-compressor and auxiliary systems: 500 kWh_e;
- Electric efficiency of the generator set: 30%;

For this, a constant methanol supply of $(500 \text{ kJ/s} / 0.4) = 1250 \text{ kJ/s}$ is required.

Considering a Calorific Value of methanol of 16 MJ/liter, a continuous supply of $1.25 / 16 = 0.078$ liter/s or 281 liter/h is to be maintained. Assuming a storage tank volume of 10 m³, roughly every **35 hours** a new supply of methanol must arrive.

Table 5-5. Emission levels associated with a methanol engine.

Emissions	Unit	Typical value
CO₂ equivalent (WTP)	kg/kWh _e	0.1 – 0.2 [13]
NO_x (TTP)	g/kWh _e	0.3
Particulate, soot	mg/kWh _e	<0.05
Other emissions		CHO (formaldehyde) can form as partial oxidation product (requires dedicated catalyst) [14]

5.4.6 Ammonia engine

Ammonia is an inorganic compound that is only liquid at room temperature under pressure or at low temperature. Ammonia, like methanol, is an energy carrier that can also be used directly as a fuel in an internal combustion engine. Ammonia is difficult to ignite and has a low combustion rate, which is why the combustion of ammonia typically takes place with diesel injection (dual fuel). Direct combustion is also possible, but this is difficult and results in low engine efficiency. Ammonia is regularly mentioned in the maritime sector, but also for use in generators by producers such as MAN and Wärtsilä (MAN Energy Solutions, 2025b; Wärtsilä, 2025).

Although ammonia contains no carbon (zero CO₂ emissions at point of use), its combustion can create NO_x from the nitrogen in the fuel/t, without mitigation, NO_x emissions can be high (like diesel levels). Combustion research shows values on the order of 5–9 g/kWh_e for NH₃ engines without mitigation measures.

In the Gasunie situation, ammonia is to be supplied from elsewhere and stored on-site. Ammonia has a lower heating value of 18.6 MJ/kg and, when liquid, 12.7 MJ/liter, that is 33% of diesel’s volumetric energy density. Also, ammonia engines are slightly less efficient, so fuel tanks must be three times larger for the same energy source.

Some basic calculations:

- Continuous power demand of the re-compressor and auxiliary systems: 500 kWh_e;
- Electric efficiency of the generator set: 30%;

For this, a constant ammonia supply of $(500 \text{ kJ/s} / 0.3) = 167 \text{ kJ/s}$ is required. Considering the Net Calorific Value of ammonia, a supply of $1.67 / 18.6 = 0,089 \text{ kg/s}$ or 323 kg/h is to be maintained.

Ammonia is extremely toxic, storing and handling of ammonia will introduce a safety risk. The 8-hr exposure limit is 25 ppmV and 300 ppmV is a life-threatening concentration.

Table 5-6. Emission levels associated with an ammonia engine.

Emissions	Unit	Typical value
CO ₂ equivalent (WTP)	kg/kWh _e	0.2
NOx (TTP)	g/kWh _e	0.2-1.0 (with SCR)
Particulate	ppm/kWh _e	0
Other emissions		Ammonia slip from engine 2-20 g NH ₃ [10]

5.4.7 Hydrogen fuel cell

Figure 5-5. Left: 250 kW hydrogen fuel cell (GeoPura, 2025). Right: the general operating principle of a fuel cell.

In a hydrogen fuel cell, hydrogen gas (H₂) is converted into electric current in an electrochemical process. This process is schematically shown in Figure 5-5 (right). Hydrogen molecules (H₂) break down into hydrogen ions (H⁺) and electrons on an anode. The hydrogen ions are transported by an electrolyte to a cathode where it is combined with oxygen from supplied air to form water. The electrons released on the anode are transported via an electrical conductor to the cathode where they are used to bring about the reaction of the hydrogen ions with oxygen. The electron transport produces an electric current that can be put to good use.

The most common form of a fuel cell is the proton-exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC). PEM fuel cells are made from advanced polymers (such as Nafion and hydrophobic PTFE), graphite (and carbon fibers), and rare earth metals (mainly platinum and ruthenium) (Hidayat et al., 2025). Fuel cells are often packaged together with control systems and batteries in a container-sized module, as shown in Figure 5-5 (left). In practical examples, the storage of hydrogen is not integrated into the container holding the fuel cell module due to the required size.

To mitigate the problem of the high required volume of fuel storage, there are some innovations that bind the hydrogen into another substance with a higher density, such as liquids. This is called a hydrogen carrier in the literature. Examples include liquids such as ammonia (NH₃), methanol (CH₃OH) and formic acid (CH₂O₂). The latter hydrogen carrier is in full development at a Dutch company, DENS, in Helmond (Dens, 2025). Formic acid has a significantly higher (energy) density than hydrogen and is therefore suitable as a storage medium. The downside is the energy loss for the conversion to and from formic acid. Nevertheless, formic acid is seen as a promising hydrogen carrier in the Netherlands (TNO, 2025b). These require conversion back to H₂ or direct fuel cell use, losses and added complexity. They are not considered further for this mobile application.

In the Gasunie situation and considering that fuel cells require higher purity hydrogen (Fuel typically >99.999% with <0.2 ppm sulfur, <5 ppm O₂) than can be provided from the pipeline to be evacuated, hydrogen is to be supplied from elsewhere and stored on-site. For hydrogen supply and storage, tube trailers can be applied. In the following example, the logistics involved in hydrogen supply are assessed.

Some basic calculations:

- Continuous power demand of the re-compressor and auxiliary systems: 500 kWhe;
- Electric efficiency of the generator set: 65%;

For this, a constant hydrogen supply of $(500 \text{ kJ/s} / 0.65) = 770 \text{ kJ/s}$ is required. Considering a Net Calorific Value of hydrogen of 119.96 MJ/kg, a continuous supply of $0.77 / 119.96 = 0.00641 \text{ kg/s}$ or 23.1 kg/h is to be maintained. Given a load capacity of 380 kg (at ≈200 bar) like in the trailer shown in the picture below, roughly every **16 hours** a new trailer must arrive.

Figure 5-6. Example of a tubular trailer with 9 steel pressure cylinders (380 kg, max 200 bar). Source: M-Tech, 2020.

Some recent developments include the use of tanks made from composite materials which allow for a higher filling pressure (up to 500, and even 750 bar(g)). This of course would extend the time between tube trailer replacements.

Table 5-7. Emission levels associated with a hydrogen fuel cell.

Emissions	Unit	Typical value
CO ₂ equivalent (WTP)	kg/kWh _e	0.05 (green)
		0.78 (gray)
NO _x (TTP)	g/kWh _e	0
Particulate	ppm/kWh _e	0

5.4.8 Batteries

Figure 5-7. 1075 kWh (500 kW peak load) Bolt-20 container (Boltainer, 2025).

Batteries store electrical energy as chemical potential energy by transferring ions from the positive electrode (cathode) to the negative electrode (anode). The most effective batteries that are widely used in emergency power applications are lithium-ion batteries, where Lithium (a metal) ion transfers the charge.

Batteries are already widely used in emergency power as part of UPS systems. However, in the Gasunie situation the battery should provide continuously power at a load of several hundred kiloWatt. A re-compressor unit is in operation during an extended period (typically days or weeks). Presently, the maximum capacity of mobile battery packs that can be obtained in the market with manageable dimensions and weight is around 1000 kWh_e. In case the re-compression unit and auxiliary systems take 500 kW_e, the above battery will last for less than two hours before having to be replaced. This would imply that there must be a 24/7 collection and delivery of battery containers during the re-compression operation, which may be considered unfeasible, let alone the time needed for fully recharging the batteries.

A battery has an energy capacity of 0.16 kWh/kg or 0.25 kWh/L. By comparison, diesel has 12 kWh/kg, and 9 kWh/l. Batteries have 1/100th the gravimetric and 1/40th the volumetric energy of diesel fuel.

In the Netherlands, there are several companies that offer battery packs in the 500 kWh-1MWh order size and that fit in a container, including Boltainer and DENS.

Unless battery performance and capacity improve drastically over the next years, the use of battery packs will not be feasible for logistical reasons. For now, this option is excluded from further investigation, apart from the purpose as discussed in the next section.

Table 5-8. Emission levels associated with batteries.

Emissions	Unit	Typical value
CO ₂ equivalent (WTP)	kg/kWh _e	0.338 (from the NL grid in 2025)
NO _x (TTP)	g/kWh _e	N/A
Particulate	ppm/kWh _e	N/A

5.4.9 Battery back-up/peak shaving functionality

From TNO’s compressor design assessment (chapter 4), it was learnt that full compressor power is only required for a limited time during evacuation activities. For the rest of the time, some 50-80% of the maximum power is needed, causing the installed power generator to be over-dimensioned for the longest part of the re-compression job. This not only brings extra rental costs, but it also causes the applied generator drive and generator to run in partial load which in general reduces energy efficiency. An exception to this are fuel cells which may perform better at a steady, partial load.

When selecting a power genset, it may be advantageous to pick a smaller sized unit (e.g. based on 80-90%) of the maximum required capacity and add a peak shaving battery instead for supplying additional power in the short time the compressor is running at maximum load. If the battery must add, say 100 kW_e, a battery as discussed in section 5.4.8 would last for some 10 hours before having to be re-charged. In the remaining time, with the compressor running in partial load, the genset’s spare capacity could be used to do the re-charging on-site without the necessity to removing the battery from the evacuation site. Once the battery is fully charged again, it could be considered to use the battery also to support the genset again, but such decision would involve a thorough analysis of gains and losses regarding spared fuel consumption versus loss of efficiency because of the genset then having to run in partial load.

Besides the peak-shaving functionality, the battery could also be used as a back-up system in case the genset is malfunctioning. It must be ensured though, whether the battery power output is high enough to take over the entire power supply. The compressor trailer is to be equipped with its own UPS, just for keeping the most essential (or critical) processes running, e.g. allowing for a controlled shut-down.

The capacity of a peak shaving/back-up battery must be adapted to the actual re-compression situation on a case-by-case basis. The adding of a peak-shaving/back-up battery of course would introduce additional logistics, a more complex power supply system and advanced planning.

5.4.10 Summary of emissions

Table 5-9. Emission levels associated with various fuels and technologies.

Generator concept	CO ₂ equivalent (WTP) kg/kWh _e	NO _x (TTP) g/kWh _e	PM mg/kWh _e	Other
Hydrogen engine	0.05 (green) 0.8 (grey)	0.5	0	Mitigation measures needed to reduce NO _x
Bio-CNG / natural gas engine	0.2 to 0.4 (depending on origin)	0.5	1-5	CH ₄ slip: 2-20 g CH ₄
HVO engine	0.12-0.2 (depending on origin)	0.36 (with SCR)	94 (unfiltered, 30% less than diesel) 1 – 10 (with DPF)	
Methanol engine	0.1 – 0.2	0.2-1.0 (with SCR)	<0.01	CHO (formaldehyde)
Ammonia engine	0.2	0.5	<0.01	NH ₃ slip: 2-20 g NH ₃
Hydrogen fuel cell	0.05 (green)	0	0	
Batteries	0.338 (from the NL grid in 2025)	N/A	N/A	

5.5 Gasunie requirements

As shown above, there are quite a few technology and fuel combinations available for generating power in off-grid situations. Some combinations are commonly used already, and others are still under development, but each combination has its own unique set of performance characteristics. There are two basic technologies left for providing power in off-grid situations, being engine/generator combinations and fuel cells. What option would prevail depends on the requirements set by Gasunie.

In the next chapter, Gasunie’s specific wishes regarding certain performance characteristics are analysed for deriving the most suitable technology/fuel combination(s).

6. Performance characteristics analysis

Gasunie has expressed the desire to keep emissions during re-compression and other evacuation activities as low as possible, even to the extent that a full emission free construction site is to be pursued. For this, several solutions could be found, but some of these are more practical than others and furthermore financial aspects connected with various solutions also play a role. To find out which Gasunie’s desires prevail, a structured approach was taken by breaking down three main performance aspects into separate sub-indicators and adding a weighing factor (0-10) to all of these. The weighing factors, an indication of the importance Gasunie gives to the various sub-indicators, were established by means of a broad internal expert consultation within Gasunie.

The three main performance factors that were used in this assessment were:

- (ecological) sustainability;
- Technical/operational feasibility;
- Business-economics viability.

For each of these main aspects, Gasunie has defined sub-performance indicators and added weighing factors to each of these. The results of this are shown in the table below.

Table 6-1. Weighing factors per performance indicator.

Sustainability	Factor	Technical/operational	Factor	Business economics	Factor
Nitrogen emissions (NOx)	6	Footprint	5	Capex	3
CO2(eq)-emissions	8	Practicality	7	Maintenance costs	3
Dust, particulate matter	6	Load range	7	Fuel costs	6
Noise	7	Start time	3	Innovation level (exposure)	2
Technology production lifecycle	4	Reliability	8	Technology obtainability	8
Fuel production lifecycle	5	Safety	10	Fuel obtainability	9
Recyclability at end of life	5	External safety	10	Additional effort on site	4
		Technology logistics	3	Technology efficiency	7
		Fuel logistics	7		
		Maintainability	2		
		Technology maturity	8		

Next, in consultation with Gasunie, DNV experts prepared a list of possible technology/fuel combinations and gave these a mark between 0 (not applicable at all) and 10 (most applicable) corresponding to the abovementioned performance indicators. The appraised technology/fuel combinations were:

- Hydrogen fuel cell;
- Hydrogen engine;
- Bio-CNG engine;
- Natural gas engine;
- Hydrotreated Vegetable Oil (HVO)-engine;
- Bio-methanol engine;
- Ammonia engine;
- Battery;
- Diesel engine (as reference).

By multiplying the allocated marks and weighing factors, for each of the three main performance aspects an overall score per technology/fuel combination has been determined, and by summation

of all results per sub-characteristic, an overall score per technology/fuel combination was calculated based on which the ranking of specific solutions was derived.

As a formula:
$$OS_{tf} = \frac{\sum_{p=1}^n (S_{tf} \times W_p)}{\sum_{p=1}^n (W_p)}$$
 with:

- OS_{tf} = Overall Score per technology/fuel combination;
- p = Performance indicator;
- n = number of identified performance indicators;
- S_{tf} = Allocated Score per technology/fuel combination;
- W_p = Weighing factor per performance characteristic.

The outcome is a performance score between 0 and 10. In the next sections, the results of this analysis are presented.

6.1 Results for the performance aspect ‘Sustainability’

In the tables below, the scores and weighing factors were combined, resulting in an overall score per technology/fuel combination.

Table 6-2. Weighed scores of the sustainability performance aspect.

Sustainability	Lifecycle						Overall score
	Nitrogen oxides	CO2(eq)	Dust	Noise	Technology	Fuel	
Weighing factor	6	10	4	7	4	4	
Score per technology/fuel							
Hydrogen fuel cell	10	10	10	10	7	9	9.54
Hydrogen engine	6	9	8	7	8	9	7.86
Bio-CNG engine	7	6	5	7	8	7	6.60
Natural gas engine	7	3	5	7	8	6	5.63
HVO-engine	6	6	4	6	8	7	6.11
Bio-methanol engine	5	7	5	7	8	7	6.54
Ammonia engine	6	7	3	6	8	6	6.17
Battery	10	10	10	10	6	9	9.43
Diesel (reference)	3	2	4	6	8	6	4.34

Where ecological sustainability is concerned, the hydrogen fuel cell has the highest overall score, closely followed by the battery solution. There is only a slight difference between both technologies when it comes to the technology lifecycle. In case of batteries, a slightly higher use of rare earth materials in the production process of the Li-Ion batteries and CO₂-emissions, compared to some elements like platinum used in fuel cells [15].

It was assumed that green power is used to produce hydrogen and charging batteries.

The hydrogen engine has a somewhat lower score, mainly because of elevated NO_x-emissions (which may be mostly mitigated by applying flue gas purification though), some hydrogen slip along the piston rings into the (ventilated) oil pan, and some dust and noise emissions.

The other engine types follow at some distance, but mutual differences are small. Compared with diesel engines, all alternative technology/fuel combinations provide better performances when it comes to sustainability.

It comes as no surprise that the traditional diesel-powered generator ended last.

6.2 Results for the performance characteristic ‘Technical/operational’

Table 6-3. Weighed scores from a technical/operational perspective.

Technical/operational							Safety		Logistics				Overall
Weighing factor		Footprint	Practicality	Load range	Start time	Reliability	Internal	External	Technology	Fuel	Maintainability	Techn. Maturity	score
		5	7	7	3	8	10	10	3	7	2	8	
Score per technology/fuel													
Hydrogen fuel cell		8	2	4	7	7	6	7	8	2	6	7	5.64
Hydrogen engine		6	9	8	8	8	6	7	8	9	8	6	7.40
Bio-CNG engine		7	7	8	8	9	7	8	8	6	8	9	7.71
Natural gas engine		7	8	8	8	9	7	8	8	9	8	9	8.11
HVO-engine		7	7	8	8	8	9	9	8	9	8	9	8.33
Bio-methanol engine		7	7	8	3	8	6	7	8	4	8	8	6.79
Ammonia engine		7	6	7	3	7	3	5	8	2	6	5	5.16
Battery		8	1	8	10	10	9	9	8	1	6	8	7.14
Diesel (reference)		7	7	8	8	9	9	9	8	9	8	10	8.56

When it comes to operational aspects, the diesel as a reference, scores best, closely followed by the HVO-fuelled engine. Both technologies are basically the same but there are some indications that HVO causes some minor side effects to the engine like drying out gaskets, hence a somewhat reduced reliability.

Of the hydrogen-based solutions, the hydrogen engine performs better than the fuel cell, mainly because of a better load range (fuel cells best can be operated at a constant, moderate load) and fuel logistics. The hydrogen suitable for engines can be obtained from the pipeline to be evacuated.

The natural gas and the bio-CNG engine perform slightly better than the hydrogen engine, especially because of a higher technical maturity level and somewhat better safety performance.

Apart from the unsurmountable issues regarding battery logistics, the battery scores well in some other respects, landing this solution in the mid-range of scores after all. *As said before, because of the logistics aspect batteries are not considered a viable option.*

6.3 Results for the performance characteristic ‘Business economics’

Table 6-4. Weighed scores from a financial-economic perspective.

Business economics		Costs			Obtainability			Technology		Overall score
Weighing factor		Capex	Maintenance	Fuel	Innovation	Technology	Fuel	Add. Effort	Efficiency	
		3	3	6	2	8	9	4	7	
Score per technology/fuel										
Hydrogen fuel cell		8	8	1	9	6	3	4	8	5.21
Hydrogen engine		5	5	3	8	3	5	7	6	4.83
Bio-CNG engine		10	7	7	2	8	10	8	6	7.74
Natural gas engine		10	7	8	2	8	10	7	6	7.79
HVO-engine		10	6	5	2	8	10	9	7	7.64
Bio-methanol engine		8	5	6	4	6	7	6	7	6.36
Ammonia engine		3	5	5	6	3	4	2	5	4.02
Battery		4	10	8	5	7	6	8	10	7.43
Diesel (reference)		10	6	10	1	10	10	9	7	8.69

From a business/economics point of view, the diesel engine performs best; the natural gas, CNG and HVO engines follow at some distance. The hydrogen fuel cell solution has poor performance when it comes to fuel costs and fuel obtainability. Also, a significant additional effort must be made in preparing the construction site for storing hydrogen and a continuous supply of tube trailers.

Note: Where Capex is mentioned, this is to be regarded as rental costs since Gasunie has indicated that the generator set will be rented for the duration of re-compression jobs.

When discarding the diesel and battery options, the following ranking per performance characteristic is found:

Table 6-5. Rankings per performance factor.

Sustainability			Technical/operational			Business economics		
Rank	Solution	Score	Rank	Solution	Score	Rank	Solution	Score
1	Hydrogen fuel cell	9.54	1	HVO-engine	8.33	1	Natural gas engine	7.79
2	Hydrogen engine	7.86	2	Natural gas engine	8.11	2	Bio-CNG engine	7.74
3	Bio-CNG engine	6.60	3	Bio-CNG engine	7.71	3	HVO-engine	7.64
4	Bio-methanol engine	6.54	4	Hydrogen engine	7.40	4	Bio-methanol engine	6.36
5	Ammonia engine	6.17	5	Bio-methanol engine	6.79	5	Hydrogen fuel cell	5.21
6	HVO-engine	6.11	6	Hydrogen fuel cell	5.64	6	Hydrogen engine	4.83
7	Natural gas engine	5.63	7	Ammonia engine	5.16	7	Ammonia engine	4.02

Based on the rankings shown in the table above, one general ranking can be derived as shown in Table 6-6.

Table 6-6. Overall ranking of various solutions.

Overall	
Rank	Solution
1	Bio-CNG engine
2	Natural gas engine
2	HVO-engine
4	Hydrogen fuel cell
4	Hydrogen engine
6	Bio-methanol engine
7	Ammonia engine

It may be concluded that the Bio-CNG engine solution obtained the highest overall ranking, followed by the natural gas and the HVO-engine. Hydrogen based solutions come at a shared fourth place. These results are derived under the assumption that each of the three main performance aspects Sustainability, Technical/operational and Business economics are all equally important to Gasunie. To come to the real weighed ranking of solutions, weighing factors should be applied to the three individual performance aspects advantaging one aspect over another. In case Gasunie values the sustainability aspects higher than for example Technical/operational aspects, the ranking may shift toward hydrogen-based solutions after all.

6.3 Conclusions

From the analyses in the previous section, it may be concluded that the battery solution is not feasible due to logistic implications. More exotic technology/fuel combinations like the bio-methanol and the ammonia option are seemingly not very suitable. Depending on the importance that Gasunie gives to the sustainability aspect connected to re-compression, either bio-CNG or HVO-engines, or hydrogen-based solutions would be most suitable. Regarding the latter it may be concluded that fuel supply and storage when using fuel cells is a serious factor to be considered.

It must be emphasized however that because of the de-coupling of the compressor drive on board the compressor trailer and the power generator set, Gasunie gains the advantage of deciding what technology/fuel combination to be applied on a case-by-case basis. Restricting factors may be the availability of suitable rental generators and obtainability and pricing of fuels.

7. Operational and maintenance aspects

7.1 Vibrations and noise of natural gas RCU's

7.1.1 Motivation

Operational experiences with existing natural gas Re-Compression Units are considered valuable input for future designs. A specific aspect of the design of reciprocating compressors is the control of pulsations and vibrations. On large, heavy-duty reciprocating compressors (API 618 machines), pulsation dampers are without exception included, to limit the transfer of pulsations from the source to the adjacent system. Also for re-compression units, that tend to be smaller in size and power, often pulsation control measures (dampers, restriction orifices) are applied. Detailed pulsation analysis of the pulsation dampers and restriction orifice plates is (necessarily) done in a generic manner, because the connected pipe system will be different from case to case. Another challenge of the different case-by-case piping hookup is the fact that the mechanical supporting of the connecting off-trailer pipework is not as robust as in permanent industrial installations. Often, the off-trailer piping is simply mounted on wooden blocks without clamping to a foundation. During design studies, often the concern on high vibrations and risk on fatigue failure on this connecting piping is raised. Even though a detailed pulsation analysis was performed for the 'first generation' RCUs of Gasunie in 2005 and 2010, actual vibrations were never inspected in the field. For the purpose of HyDelta4, and to support the design of the 'next generation' natural gas RCUs, to be commissioned in 2026, a field test was organized.

7.1.2 RCU description

Gasunie has 2 Re-Compression Units for application in evacuation jobs. Both units are very comparable (but not identical) in design. The compressors are 4-throw design Dresser Rand reciprocating compressors, with 2 active cylinders (the alternative side of the compressor frame has dummy counter-weights). The compressors are of the type Valve-In-Piston (VIP). The compressors are operated at the fixed compressor speed of 1800 rpm, are lubricated and gas-engine driven. Originally the trailers were designed to be used as separate, parallel units. Each machine could be operated in 1-stage (cylinders in parallel) and 2-stage mode (cylinders in series). However, later in the operation, the compressors were modified, to be used also in 'tandem' operation. This serial use of the trailers allowed for evacuation to lower end pressures. For pressure down to 20 bar(g), the parallel configuration of the trailers is used, each running in 1-stage mode (Figure 7-1). Next, for pressures down to 7-10 bar(g) the parallel configuration of the trailers is used, each running in 2-stage mode. Finally, for suction pressures below 7 bar(g), the tandem mode is used. Here the trailers are used in series, with RCU1 in 1-stage, and RCU2 in 2-stage mode (Figure 7-2).

Tandem Parallel bedrijf
(Systeem-zuigdruk 66 - 17 barg)

Figure 7-1. Illustration of parallel operation of RCUs, both in 1-stage configuration.

Tandem Serie bedrijf
Fase 3 (Systeem-zuigdruk 20- 1 barg)

Figure 7-2. Illustration of tandem operation of RCUs, RUC1 in 1-stage configuration, RUC2 in 2-stage configuration.

7.1.3 Test program

A pipeline evacuation was scheduled in June 2025, on Gasunie’s compressor station Ommen. The two natural gas compressor trailers (RCU1 and RCU2) were mobilized for the evacuation job. The dedicated tests included recording of vibrations and noise levels at various locations on and around the units. A test was done at the early phase of evacuation. This test was repeated at a later phase of the evacuation. The measurement program for the two series is summarized in Table 7-1 and Table 7-2.

Table 7-1. Measurement series 1, parallel operation.

19-6-2025	RCU1			RCU2		
	Suction	Stage 1 discharge	Stage 2 discharge	Suction	Stage 1 discharge	Stage 2 discharge
Start	47.3	56.6	56.4	48.4	56.6	56.2
End	46.3	56.4	56.2	47.3	56.4	56.0

Table 7-2. Measurement series 2, tandem operation, RCU in 1-stage mode RCU2 in 2-stage mode.

26-6-2025	RCU1			RCU2		
	Suction	Stage 1 discharge	Stage 2 discharge	Suction	Stage 1 discharge	Stage 2 discharge
Start	5.5	10.3	10.2	10.2	23.2	55.6
End	5.4	10.1	10.0	10.1	22.8	55.6

The installation is illustrated in Figure 7-3 and Figure 7-4. RCU1 was installation on the concrete pavement, while RCU2 was placed on driving plates, on grass.

Figure 7-3. Hook-up of Re-Compression Units, flexible hoses and temporary interconnecting piping.

Figure 7-4. Illustration of connections to the RCUs.

The vibration orientation is defined as follows, see also:

- X = axial direction trailer
- Y = perpendicular to trailer
- Z = Vertical

Figure 7-5. Top view of trailers with orientation of vibrations.

7.1.4 Vibration measurement results - trailer

Vibration measurements were taken on the trailer key points, see Figure 7-6. The vibration levels are shown in Table 7-3. The colours are applied in accordance with the severity classification in the ISO-20816-8 standard (assuming the limit levels for a compressor foundation). The vibrations are highest for RCU 2, in particular for measurement series 1. The vibrations are dominated by the 1st order of the compressor running speed (1800 RPM → 30 Hz), see Figure 7-7. In general the vibration amplitudes are judged as low, considering the particular mechanical supporting of the trailer (being relatively resilient, compared to a concrete foundation).

Figure 7-6. Measurement points on trailer key points.

Table 7-3. Measurement results on the trailer (RMS values in mm/s).

ID	Location	Series 1 - 1 stage mode			Series 2 - 3-stage mode		
		X	Y	Z	X	Y	Z
1	MHC1, trailer	1.1	1.7	2.1	0.7	1.1	1.8
2	MHC1, trailer	1.3	2.3	1.8	0.8	1.5	1.9
3	MHC1, trailer	1.1	1.8	4.1	0.7	1.2	2.9
4	MHC1, trailer	1.5	0.7	5.1	0.8	0.4	3.1
5	MHC1, trailer	0.5	1.9	0.8	0.5	2.4	0.8
6	MHC1, trailer	1.0	1.9	1.2	0.7	2.3	1.0
7	MHC1, trailer	1.0	0.6	2.8	0.6	0.4	3.6
8	MHC1, trailer	1.2	1.8	2.0	0.7	1.2	2.2
9	MHC1, trailer	1.0	2.3	2.1	0.7	1.4	1.3
10	MHC1, trailer	0.7	1.6	1.6	0.5	1.1	1.3
11	MHC2, trailer	2.1	2.0	5.2	1.5	1.6	3.4
12	MHC2, trailer	2.1	2.8	2.7	1.6	2.0	2.0
13	MHC2, trailer	1.7	2.9	3.5	1.5	1.9	2.7
14	MHC2, trailer	1.3	2.1	7.0	0.9	1.3	4.3
15	MHC2, trailer	1.3	4.6	3.9	0.9	2.9	2.3
16	MHC2, trailer	1.8	4.7	4.3	1.3	3.2	2.6
17	MHC2, trailer	2.0	1.9	3.7	1.2	1.3	3.1
18	MHC2, trailer	1.9	2.7	6.6	1.2	1.7	4.5
19	MHC2, trailer	0.8	2.7	4.0	0.7	1.9	1.2
20	MHC2, trailer	0.9	2.1	1.6	0.7	1.6	1.6

Figure 7-7. Typical example, series 1, measurement point 14 (RCU 2), vibration level dominated by the 1st order of the compressor speed (30 Hz).

7.1.5 Vibration measurement results - trailer

Vibration measurements were taken on the compressor area (various points on dampers, cylinders and frame). The results are shown in Table 7-4 and Table 7-5, with the colouring in accordance with the limit values in the ISO 20816-8 standard. Again, the highest vibrations are dominated by the 1st order of the compressor speed. Again, it is observed that vibrations are higher on RCU2, in particular around the 2nd cylinder. On this particular cylinder (that was re-fit around 2016 for application in tandem operation) the vibration levels exceed the target values in ISO-20816-8. These increased vibration levels are not observed on the other cylinder of RCU2, nor on RCU1.

Table 7-4. Measurement results in compressor area - cylinders, dampers (RMS values in mm/s).

		Series 1 - 1 stage mode			Series 2 - 3-stage mode		
21	MHC 1, suction damper of cylinder 1	12.0	3.4	9.4	10.5	1.6	5.1
22	MHC 1, suction damper of cylinder 1	12.8	9.1	10.6	11.0	3.8	4.7
23	MHC 1, cylinder 1	11.6	5.4	10.2	10.8	4.6	7.2
24	MHC 1, skid beam connected to support of cylinder 1	3.8	4.9	4.9	1.5	3.3	3.2
25	MHC 1, nozzle on discharge damper of cylinder 1	9.3	10.0	7.1	10.7	7.3	4.8
26	MHC 1, discharge damper cylinder 1	8.6	5.9	6.7	5.1	4.4	4.8
27	MHC 1, suction damper of cylinder 2	7.2	2.7	6.3	5.8	1.9	5.2
28	MHC 1, suction damper of cylinder 2	7.2	2.7	6.3	5.8	1.9	5.2
29	MHC 1, cylinder 2	9.0	5.4	15.7	6.7	4.2	10.1
30	MHC 1, skid beam connected to support of cylinder 2	5.3	7.5	4.5	1.8	3.5	3.7
31	MHC 1, nozzle on discharge damper of cylinder 2	8.5	12.2	11.3	6.2	14.4	10.5
32	MHC 1, discharge damper cylinder 2	7.7	4.0	6.9	4.5	4.5	3.6
33	MHC 1, frame top, at dummy cylinder driven end	6.7	7.4	2.7	5.0	5.6	2.7
34	MHC 1, frame bottom, at dummy cylinder driven end	1.7	3.9	3.9	1.7	3.3	3.0
35	MHC 2, suction damper of cylinder 1	12.8	9.6	8.6	14.8	10.7	7.3
36	MHC 2, suction damper of cylinder 1	12.9	13.3	13.2	14.5	8.7	6.8
37	MHC 2, cylinder 1	13.6	7.3	19.0	12.3	5.6	10.9
38	MHC 2, skid beam connected to support of cylinder 1	4.3	12.1	9.7	2.9	7.6	5.6
39	MHC 2, nozzle on discharge damper of cylinder 1	9.6	8.7	5.9	9.5	7.7	6.0
40	MHC 2, discharge damper cylinder 1	9.3	4.1	7.7	7.5	6.1	5.3
41	MHC 2, suction damper of cylinder 2	25.3	16.5	19.2	15.6	6.7	8.4
42	MHC 2, suction damper of cylinder 2	26.7	13.0	11.9	15.5	7.1	7.9
43	MHC 2, cylinder 2	23.4	6.1	13.9	13.1	5.6	8.3
44	MHC 2, skid beam connected to support of cylinder 2	4.2	11.6	9.9	1.8	9.3	3.5
45	MHC 2, nozzle on discharge damper of cylinder 2	15.2	7.5	9.4	9.5	8.3	6.1
46	MHC 2, discharge damper cylinder 2	13.6	5.1	18.5	8.5	3.4	9.2
47							
48							
49	MHC 2, frame top, at dummy cylinder driven end	4.0	8.7	3.2	2.9	4.8	3.0
50	MHC 2, frame bottom, at dummy cylinder driven end	3.2	4.2	3.6	1.9	3.0	2.9

Table 7-5. Measurement results in compressor area - piping (RMS values in mm/s).

		Series 1 - 1 stage mode			Series 2 - 3-stage mode		
59	MHC1, suction piping on trailer	2.8	1.4	1.2	2.5	2.2	1.1
60	MHC1, suction piping on trailer	1.9	2.8	2.9	2.7	2.4	4.6
61	MHC1, suction piping on trailer	2.9	5.3	5.8	3.9	5.4	5.9
62	MHC2, suction piping on trailer	7.3	3.5	5.2	4.7	2.8	3.4
63	MHC2, suction piping on trailer	5.1	7.8	5.9	2.8	5.4	3.4
64	MHC2, suction piping on trailer	6.1	13.5	5.9	6.7	9.6	4.8
70	MHC1, discharge piping on trailer	3.0	4.2	1.0	1.9	3.0	0.9
71	MHC1, discharge piping on trailer	3.4	4.2	4.4	3.2	3.1	3.6
72	MHC2, discharge piping on trailer	4.4	5.9	2.5	2.0	4.3	1.3
73	MHC2, discharge piping on trailer	9.6	6.3	13.9	3.6	4.8	7.9
74	MHC1, top outboard support cylinder 1				8.7	5.3	9.0
75	MHC1, bottom outboard support cylinder 1				8.3	5.3	9.4
76	MHC1, top outboard support cylinder 2				6.5	5.2	9.0
77	MHC1, bottom outboard support cylinder 2				6.5	4.9	8.8
78	MHC2, top outboard support cylinder 1				11.0	6.3	8.0
79	MHC2, bottom outboard support cylinder 1				10.3	6.1	7.9
80	MHC2, top outboard support cylinder 2				11.9	6.0	9.3
81	MHC2, bottom outboard support cylinder 2				11.7	6.1	6.0

Figure 7-8. Vibration level on suction damper on cylinder 2 of RCU2, series 1..

7.1.6 Vibration measurement results – temporary piping

Vibration measurements were taken on the temporary piping that does not have a permanent, robust supporting layout (Figure 7-3). All vibration levels in this area are far below the acceptance standard. The main reasons are the application of flexible connecting hoses: these ensure an efficient mechanical de-coupling from the trailer but also an acoustic attenuation of pulsations originating from the compressors.

Table 7-6. Measurement results on temporary piping with ad-hoc supporting layout (RMS values in mm/s).

		Series 1 - 1 stage mode			Series 2 - 3-stage mode		
51	Suction field piping	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
52	Suction field piping	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
53	Suction field piping	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3
54	Suction field piping	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.3
55	Suction field piping	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.1
56	Suction field piping	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1
57	Suction field piping	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1
58	Suction field piping	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.2	0.5	0.2
65	Discharge field piping	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2
66	Discharge field piping	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.1
67	Discharge field piping	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.2	0.3	0.2
68	Discharge field piping	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.2
69	Discharge field piping	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.2
82	Discharge piping, on wooden beam support near location V69				0.2	0.2	0.2
83	Discharge piping, on asphalt near wooden beam support near location V69				0.5	0.3	0.1
84	Discharge piping, on wooden beam support near location V66				0.1	0.2	0.1
85	Discharge piping, on asphalt near wooden beam support near location V66				0.1	0.1	0.1
86	Suction piping, on wooden beam support near location V56				0.3	0.2	0.2
87	Suction piping, on asphalt near wooden beam support near location V56				0.1	0.0	0.1

7.1.7 Noise measurement results

Noise measurements were taken in and around various locations on the trailers. The locations are shown in Figure 7-9, and the results are shown in Table 7-7. Noise levels inside the RCU enclosure reach 101 dB(A), with noise enclosure doors opened. Measurement locations close to the RCUs with noise doors closed) exceed the 85 dB(A) limit; hearing protection at these locations is mandatory. With increased distance to the RCUs, the noise level reduces, for example 64 dB(A) at 40 meter. The noise spectra are dominated by frequencies related to the compressor speed and its higher orders.

Figure 7-9. Noise measurement locations.

Table 7-7. Noise levels, in dB(A).

Location	Series 1	Series 2
1	100,6	98,3
2	100,5	99,9
3	88,8	87,7
4	82,9	82,3
5	66,8	67,3
6	71,5	71,8
7	61,2	61,7
8		84,3
9		87,7
10		60,0
11		66,4
12		60,2
13		69,6
14		64,3

7.2 Operation and maintenance

Gasunie already owns two re-compression units for evacuating natural gas pipelines for 20+ years and during that time vast experience in operating these units was gained. The re-compressors are operated by the Gasunie’s department ‘Special Operations’ located in Deventer, where also the re-compressor units are kept when not in use.

Depending on the situation per evacuation job, one single or two parallel compressor units are used in an effort to achieve the lowest suction pressure at the end of the job in the shortest possible time. Achieving the lowest possible suction pressure will reduce the amount of natural gas remaining inside the pipeline and therefore CO₂-emissions caused by flaring, or methane emissions by venting the residual natural gas. Important aspects to consider when planning an evacuation job are:

- Length and diameter of the pipeline section to be evacuated;
- Available time for completing the job;
- Profit/cost ratio, also considering (residual) emissions;
- Available space at the construction site;
- Location of the construction site (e.g. near urban areas);
- Specific identified risks and safety distances to be maintained.

Especially achieving the lowest possible suction pressure is quite a challenge for the present re-compression units. Depending on the circumstances, suction pressures of 2-6 barg are feasible at the moment, but past studies have shown that lower pressures using the present units are not achievable due to geometrical limitations of the applied compressors. For achieving lower suction pressures, a separate (screw) booster compressor would have to be used but introducing all kinds of complications during installation and operation.

In some cases, depending on the natural gas volume to be displaced, it may not be worth the effort to install and operate a re-compressor. In such situations most of the time a combination of flaring and venting is used to de-pressurise pipeline section of interest. The decision on whether or not to apply re-compression is to be made on a case-by-case basis, based on the knowledge and experience of the planners of such specialised jobs.

Lately, DNV has developed a decision-making tool for Gasunie with which the balance between prevented and produced carbon emissions during evacuation jobs can be calculated. With this model planners are able to determine what evacuation method would prevail considering carbon emissions. Besides stand-alone solutions like flaring & venting, nitrogen purging or stoppling (with flaring and venting), also options involving re-compressions are mutually compared based on overall emission levels.

The model contains a module in which the decades long experience of re-compressor operators is included, translated into 'typical' evacuation situations. Depending on the various input parameters to be fed into the model, it shows the options with the least produced emissions, also including (more or less emission free) construction site preparations and transport of equipment and fuels. The main purpose of the model is to assess the extent to which emissions involved in reparation of leakages inside the transmission network outweigh the produced emissions during evacuation jobs meant to able repairs. Based on the outcomes, leak repairs are prioritized.

A similar model of course could also be applied in case of hydrogen filled pipelines.

In TNO's concept no. 1, a suction pressure of some 2 bar(a) seems feasible, but it has to be appreciated that the remaining hydrogen inside the pipeline can be easily removed by means of flaring, without causing carbon emissions. Only the last of the hydrogen remaining inside at a pressure too low to be combusted inside the flare would have to be vented into the atmosphere, e.g. by means of air moving. In this respect, only the monetary value of the lost commodity provides the incentive to keep the flared and vented hydrogen volume at a minimum.

Fuel and power supply

As said in chapter 5.1, fuel supply using a direct compressor drive would be the easiest to achieve. The fuel required for powering the compressor can directly obtained from the suction side of the compressor, also helping to speed up the evacuation process.

Using an indirect drive implies that the re-compressor unit is to be provided with electricity, meaning that power cables are to be running between the generator set and the compressor trailer. A safe

positioning and connection of these cables will cause additional work, and it must be made sure that the cables don't cause any tripping danger.

The generator set requires fuel lines to be running from the fuel supply to the generator. In case of a hydrogen engine powered generator, a separate (flexible) line from the hydrogen pipeline to the generator set must be constructed. For any other fuel, a separate fuel depot is to be established at some distance from the generator and other equipment, depending on the required safety distances.

Adding cables, hoses and pipelines to the construction site will introduce additional safety risks which should be addressed during the planning and preparation phase of the evacuation project.

It may be expected that maintenance of the compressor units will be less demanding than in the current situation with the natural gas re-compressors. The compressors themselves will require similar care as the present ones, mainly consisting of:

- Regular oil change;
- Cleansing or replacement of filters and separators;
- Regular replacement of piston rings and valve seats;
- Bearing inspection;
- Calibration of measurement instruments;
- ESD-tests;
- Cleansing of the chillers.

In case dry-friction piston rings are used, replacement of these is expected to be more frequent than in case of lubricated rings.

Maintenance requiring opening of the compressor is to be done by a specialized firm, but this also depends on the warranty arrangements that are made with the compressor supplier or packager.

It can be concluded that the electric motor will require much less maintenance than the presently used gas engines. Replacement of block brushes may be required after a certain number of operating hours (if used in the first place), but this is a minor activity. Also the motor bearings may need to be inspected/replaced after a certain period of time.

All electrical equipment, including the VSD/VFD and the UPSs must be tested at regular intervals.

A major advantage of using rental gensets is that maintenance of these lies fully with the rental companies. Maintenance costs however will be included in the rental tariffs.

References

- [1] *HyDelta Vierde Tranche, 2025-2026*, Samenwerkingsverband HyDelta, 2025.
- [2] *Machinery and Energy Systems for the Hydrogen Economy*, Klaus Brun (ed), Elsevier, 2022.
- [3] EFRC, *Hydrogen compression - Boosting the energy transition*, <https://www.recip.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/2022-EFRC-WhitePaper-Hydrogen-Compression.pdf>: European Forum for Reciprocating Compressors, 2022.
- [4] J. Garcia, *State of the art, technology readiness, and technical considerations around hydrogen compression systems for large-scale offshore application*, HyTros D4.3.1, 2025.
- [5] *API 618 standard - Reciprocating Compressors for Petroleum, Chemical and Gas Industry Services (6th edition)*, American Petroleum Institute, 2024.
- [6] *API 619 standard - Rotary-Type Positive-Displacement Compressors for Petroleum, Petrochemical and Natural Gas Industries (5th edition)*, American Petroleum Institute, 2010.
- [7] *API 617 standard – Axial and Centrifugal Compressors and Expander-Compressors (9th edition)*, American Petroleum Institute, 2022.
- [8] M. Laignel, R. Oung, J. Neveu and A. Vucher, “H2 efficient and near zero emissions operation on a SI PFI heavy duty single cylinder engine,” *Int. J. Hydrog. Energy*, vol. 128, pp. 105-116, 2025.
- [9] G. Geletukha, *Feasibility Study and Life Cycle Assessment of Biomethane Production from Intermediate Crops in Ukraine*, New York: Social Science Research Network, Rochester, 2025.
- [10] N. Kuittinen, M. Heikkilä and K. Lehtoranta, *Review of Methane Slip from LNG Engines*.
- [11] *PG_UseCase_HVO_Datacenter.pdf*, <https://www.mtu-solutions.com>, 2026.
- [12] R. Vermeule, *Effects of HVO on pollutant emissions of Stage V non-road diesel engines*, TNO, 2025.
- [13] H. Carlo, *Carbon footprint of methanol*, Methanol Institute, https://www.studiogearup.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/2022_sGU-for-MI_Methanol-carbon-footprint-DEF-1.pdf, 2022.
- [14] S. Mashruk, “Perspectives on NOx Emissions and Impacts from Ammonia Combustion Processes,” *Energy Fuels*, vol. 38(20), p. 19253019292, 2024.
- [15] J. W. X. W. X. Z. B. W. W. Y. F. Y. R. Y. X. L. a. G. H. Wenjie Zhang, “Comparison of life cycle assessment in the fuel cell industry chain and the lithium battery industry,” *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*, no. 40, 2025, 2025.

[16] N. González Díez, “Impact of high speed hydrogen flow on system integrity and noise,” HyDelta 1, 2021.